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**Muffet McGraw
Designates \$10,000 to
Neurodegenerative
Disease Research**

PAGE 12

**HBO's *The Last of Us*:
Fact or Fiction?**

PAGE 18

**Coping with COVID-19:
Interpersonal Post-
Pandemic Adjustments**

PAGE 30

**An Accessible
Quantitative Exploration
of Gravitational Lensing**

PAGE 43

SCIENCE

Table of Contents

Letter from the Dean

- 3 Perspective in Research
—Dr. Michael Hildreth, Vice President, Associate Provost, and Dean of the Notre Dame Graduate School
- 4 Letter from the Editors
—Alexandra Noble and Emily Hunt

News

- 12 Former Head Women's Basketball Coach Muffet McGraw Designates \$10,000 Honorarium to Del Valle Lab for Neurodegenerative Disease Research
—Sisy Chen and Emily Hunt
- 13 GEM Fellowship Awarded to Computational Biology Doctoral Student Studying Neurodegenerative Diseases
—Grace Galfano
- 14 Accidental Discovery of a 'Raspberry-Shaped' Nanoparticle May Advance Precision Drug Delivery
—James Lazar
- 15 Students Return from a Once-in-a-Lifetime Trip to the Galápagos Islands
—Annie Benn
- 16 Exploring the Molecular Basis for Racial Disparities in Cancer Outcomes
—Brooke Friedman
- 17 Notre Dame Engineers and Microbiologists at Trinity College Dublin Unite to Improve Cystic Fibrosis Treatment
—Alyssa Fiume
- 18 HBO's *The Last of Us*: Fact or Fiction? A Deep Dive into Fungal Infections and Dr. Santiago-Tirado's Research
—Alexandra Noble
- 20 Wastewater-Based Epidemiology on Mpx Detection
—Christalia Barone

Spotlights

- 6 Faculty Spotlights
- 52 Student/Alumni Spotlights

Chemistry & Biochemistry

- 22 The Effects of Kinase Inhibition on the Stability of Biomolecular Condensates, Microtubule-Regulating Structures Composed of Plus-End Tracking Proteins
—Noah Abel Baca

Health, Medicine, & Neuroscience

- 27 Event-Related Potentials in Emotions Attention: A Literature Review
—Sarah Berland
- 30 Coping with COVID-19: The Relationship of Interpersonal Mindfulness and Parent Adjustment to the Pandemic
—Jessica Davis

Biology & Environmental Sciences

- 36 Participation of SOCS Proteins in Multiple Sclerosis and Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis
—John Hlavin, Virginia Sedeño-Monge
- 40 Sleep Duration Variability Moderates the Effect of Cortisol Reactivity on Negative Affect in Adolescents
—Brooke Friedman, Linhao Zhang, Asaaf Oshri

Physics

- 43 An Accessible Quantitative Exploration of Gravitational Lensing
—Emma Laboe, Will Peeler, Jackson White

Mathematics

- 48 Determinantal Inequalities in Minors of Totally Positive Matrices
—Julian Kaufmann, Jack Hertzog, Emma Laboe, Yutan Zhang

Perspective in Research: *A Letter from Dean Hildreth*

Dear College of Science Undergraduates,

As I look back at the beginnings of my academic trajectory, it hardly seems likely that I would be writing this introduction after having reached a leadership position at a university like Notre Dame. Funny things happen when you pursue science with determined curiosity and a passion for learning.

I went to university intending to become an engineer, since that was the only “practical” career that involved science and building things that I knew about. Because of previous coursework, I ended up taking advanced physics classes as a first-year student and was immediately seduced by the beauty of the mathematics that could describe our physical world. I switched over to a major in physics at the end of my first semester. I never did take an engineering course.

That switch, however, was merely the first fateful turn on my career path. The second came during my sophomore year, when I was connected to the high energy particle physics group which needed students to help build a particle physics experiment. Swapping my work-study job from cooking breakfast in the dining hall to building a particle physics experiment seemed like a good move. In reality, I spent the first several months in relative tedium, polishing pieces of clear plastic. These weren’t just any pieces of plastic, though: These would be used to channel light produced by subatomic particles from the interior of a giant magnet out to sensitive detectors.

My gut reaction when I first heard about particle physics was, “Why would anyone actually study that?” However, the plastic polishing turned into a summer job (with more plastic polishing, but also electronics) during which the graduate students were forced to give us undergrads short talks on particle physics and the experiment we were building. These presentations were fascinating, giving us a glimpse into the subatomic universe. The fact that the detectors we were building could allow one to “see” individual subatomic particles moving through space and then allow us to watch them decay was amazing. It still amazes me to this day that this is possible. After that summer, I was hooked.

Thirty-seven years later, exploring the basic building blocks of matter and probing the secrets of the universe is still compelling work! I have followed many different scientific threads over this time. By chance, my Ph.D. adviser was also deeply involved in studying future particle accelerators and accelerator instrumentation, which led to me heading a handful of projects at various particle physics labs studying beam energy measurements, and a membership in a whole different community of physicists. An interest in and facility with software and computing led to many different leadership roles overseeing the development of advanced software for particle physics experiments, including my current role guiding software and computing research and development for the future running of the Large Hadron Collider at CERN. Somewhere along the way, I also discovered a passion for teaching, and realized that teaching and research enhance each other. This has also led to membership in a network of colleagues scattered across the world who are equally devoted to advancing student learning.

What lessons can you draw from this? First, approaching life with a high level of curiosity and an open mind can take you to fantastic places. For me, engaging in research opened my eyes to a universe I didn’t know existed, and set me on a career path that has stretched over many decades. Second, nothing is linear. In whatever you do, there will be setbacks, detours, wrong turns, and roadblocks. For me, the science has always been so compelling that I wanted to press on. Third, embrace the detours. Each seemingly random turn can lead to a whole new world of colleagues and knowledge that was previously invisible. For me, the paths less trodden have sometimes been the most rich and interesting. Finally, good mentors and colleagues are critical to your future. The myth of a lone investigator making stunning and original discoveries is just that, a myth. Science is a collaborative enterprise, so be deliberate in finding good collaborators who can guide and sustain your work.

As you peruse this issue of *Scientia*, pause to admire the work of your peers, but also draw inspiration from their efforts. Think about how you can contribute to this vast enterprise we call “science.” Think about how a research experience might shape your life. Be open to the spark!

In Notre Dame,

Michael D. Hildreth, Ph.D.
Vice President, Associate Provost, and Dean of the Notre Dame Graduate School

Letter from the Editors

A challenge that remains and perpetually continues to face us not only as a collective scientific community, but as a greater whole, is the journey of returning to normal after COVID — but what does this look like after our world has been permanently and radically changed forever? The pandemic has launched us into a new world, a new galaxy, if you will. However, we are still marked by remains of a past that continues to maim us, as seen in the COVID-19–centered manuscripts and Talk Science discussions featured throughout this year’s 2023 edition...four years later.

However, returning to normalcy has given us the opportunity to do venture into endeavors never done before. It has united us as a community and forced us to pay attention to social, structural, and scientific issues that have been previously ignored.

This year provided the opportunity to do the unprecedented during unprecedented times, as exhibited throughout this issue. Fungal infections to the forefront of not only public health research, but the interconnectedness across greater societal and media landscape, as discussed in our article “HBO’s *The Last of Us*: Fact or Fiction?” Notre Dame engineers worked relentlessly to initiate global connections to fight cystic fibrosis. Seen in the fact that for the first time we have included global literature reviews from students who have done research on opposite ends of the planet.

While COVID shook the world, the scientific community responded with vigor. This year gave us a cultural reset. An opportunity to start anew and define for ourselves what we want our new normal to look like. We have been led to adapt and evolve — to elucidate what this reset looks like and explore what lies beyond what we once believed were limits. This year, *Scientia* hosted its first Talk Science in the Jordan Hall of Science Digital Visualization Theater with Dr. Keith Davis. We saw how like the sun, we are also stars that have managed to emerge under pressure through murky gas and dust. All the bright students, faculty, and affiliates who worked tirelessly to make this student publication possible have showcased how Notre Dame continues to shine its light.

We are pleased to continue the *Scientia* legacy with Volume 14 this spring. We hope this edition inspires you to think creatively and outside of the box. To not only continue to foster and engage an inclusive and empowering community of budding scientists of all backgrounds, but to challenge you how to think about what makes you shine bright and how you’ll shape your own personal destiny and galaxy. Because our love and our passion, our hearts can change galaxies.

We would like to express our sincere gratitude to the nearly 100 Notre Dame College of Science affiliates who came together to make this issue possible and to you, our beloved readers. A special thank-you goes out to the editorial board and staff for their unwavering commitment and hard work, which have played a vital role in the successful publication of our journal. An additional special thank you goes out to our outreach coordinator, Rebecca Boyle, whose dedication and passion for the sciences were instrumental to making this publication a success. Our gratitude also goes to our adviser, Dr. Xuemin Lu, and the College of Science Marketing Communications team, including Lotta Barnes, Deanna Ferrell, and Tammi Freehling, whose guidance and support have been invaluable. We are excited to see how *Scientia* will continue to grow and inspire in the coming years, and we are exceptionally confident in the passing of the Editor-in-Chief roles to Kayla Nguyen and Stephanie Swegle.

In Notre Dame,

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*Issue cover photo courtesy of *Scientia* member and undergraduate Quinn Mackay during the Talk Science event in the Digital Visualization Theater.

College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Alvaro Acosta-Serrano

AUTHOR: ANTHONY TRAVLOS

When asked about his work, Dr. Alvaro Acosta-Serrano declared that the keys to his success were passion and resilience. He formulates a specific research question and emphasizes pursuing a complete response. What is Dr. Serrano's passion that drives his questions? Parasitology and vector-borne diseases.

Born and raised in Venezuela, Dr. Serrano developed his interest in parasitology through observing the detrimental effects vector-borne diseases had on Venezuelan society and the lack of infrastructure to address the issue. However, vector-borne diseases are not isolated to Venezuela. Today, vector-borne diseases cause more than 700,000 deaths annually (1). To combat this global problem, Dr. Serrano's lab focuses on kinetoplastid parasites and their vectors, along with molecular solutions to control and prevent parasite transmission. The lab studies African trypanosome parasites and tsetse flies specifically as vectors.

Trypanosoma brucei, a type of African trypanosome, causes African trypanosomiasis, more commonly known as "sleeping sickness," a parasitic disease that is transmitted to humans by tsetse fly bites. Sleeping sickness causes a variety of symptoms including fever, joint pain, behavior changes, and, if not treated, death. No vaccine for sleeping sickness exists and treatments are often hard for at-risk populations which predominantly exist in third-world countries. Thus, there is a high demand for a strategy to control and prevent transmission.

Recently, Dr. Serrano has investigated various pathways for vector control, one being the tyrosine catabolism pathway, a highly conserved pathway in eukaryotic species. When vectors ingest blood, tyrosine is produced, which is toxic. To combat this toxicity, vectors possess two enzymes that degrade tyrosine, tyrosine aminotransferase (TAT) and 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate dioxygenase (HPPD). Serrano's lab examined the effect of the HPPD inhibitor drug nitisinone (NTBC) on the tyrosine catabolic pathway and ensuing tsetse fly survival.

To test the efficacy of NTBC on tsetse fly survival, Dr. Serrano's lab fed rats an oral dose of NTBC and allowed tsetse flies to feed on the rats' blood. After about eight hours, flies displayed paralysis, and after 26 hours, approximately 90% of flies died. Furthermore, NTBC is only harmful to blood-feeding insects, has low toxicity to mammals, requires a low dose, and is environmentally sustainable—all factors that make NTBC an optimal treatment against transmission of *Trypanosoma brucei*. Mathematical modeling suggests that drug administration every 30 days to humans and livestock in high-risk areas could control the transmission of African trypanosomiasis.

Although these findings are recent and there is still a long way to go before implementations of tyrosine catabolism inhibitor treatments, the findings of this experiment spark excitement to further study the control of African trypanosomiasis transmission. Regarding the importance of his work, Dr. Serrano indicated these studies are "important for most needed societies" and the "science is not separate from social justice." Dr. Serrano repeatedly emphasizes the importance of helping those most in need as this drives the most impactful science.

Aside from all his work, Dr. Serrano declares his proudest accomplishment to be his "training and mentorship of the new generation," which he hopes will help continue his work for generations to come in pursuit of truth and hope for bettering the world.

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College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Paul Kulesa

AUTHOR: ANTHONY TRAVLOS

The University of Notre Dame College of Science preaches “building upon our past to build a better future for all.” Very few researchers embody this mission more than Dr. Paul Kulesa. Dr. Kulesa, an undergraduate alumnus from Notre Dame, received a bachelor of science degree in aerospace engineering and then went on to work as a NASA engineer. Dr. Kulesa returned to graduate school where he realized that biology, and not aerospace engineering, might be his passion.

Dr. Kulesa completed his Ph.D. in computational applied mathematics and conducted a postdoctoral fellowship specializing in embryology. Through his graduate studies and postdoctoral fellowship, Dr. Kulesa made the transition from a physical to experimental scientist so he could not only analyze data, but collect his own data as well. When asked about the uniqueness of his journey, Dr. Kulesa attributed his knack for innovation to his engineering background. “Being naïve worked,” he said. Creating and testing solutions to complex problems was something Dr. Kulesa enjoyed, and he wanted to steer that passion toward investigating health issues.

Dr. Kulesa now investigates cell migration in the neural crest during vertebrate development using Aves as a model system. Kulesa’s lab works to identify the multitude of complex mechanisms of regulatory signals for neural crest migration with the long-term goal of better comprehending neural crest-related birth defects, specifically neuroblastoma cancer. Furthermore, the lab uses spatial transcriptomics—a method for mapping gene activity—along with advanced in vivo imaging and image analysis to perform in vivo time-lapse studies of neural crest cell migration. Finally, computational models are tested to verify patterns and predictions in cell migration.

The neural crest, Dr. Kulesa’s main in vivo model, is an invasive stem cell population that travels throughout the vertebrate embryo. Neural crest cells are popular cell models due to their similarities of cell migration to metastatic cancer cells. Recently, Dr. Kulesa, along with a team of other scientists, molecularly

characterized the neural crest cells within the first four chick cranial to cardiac branchial arches (1). A combination of sequence analysis as well as in situ fluorescence findings revealed 45 genes in common with published invasion cell lines suggesting the potential for a discovery of foundational properties behind development and cancer metastasis. To test the similarity between the 45 gene cell invasion signature’s relevance to human neuroblastoma, three human neuroblastoma cell lines were implanted into chick embryos. The highly invasive neuroblastoma cells upregulated 33% of the 45 genes, suggesting a potential correlation between number and type of genes upregulated and cancer metastasis.

Ultimately, Dr. Kulesa’s studies of neural crest cell migration in model systems provide insight to further derive mechanisms of cancer metastasis, one of the largest unanswered questions in science. However, comprehension of mechanisms is simply the first step in cancer research. The goal is that one day, the research done on a simple chick embryo may lead to more accurate cancer risk assessments, therapeutic targets, and cancer cell inhibitors that can change the future of medicine. Regarding his work, Dr. Kulesa commented, “At NASA we were working to create a lunar colony, but we don’t fully understand cell migration in embryos.” Maybe instead of looking up to the stars, it is time to look inward to make new discoveries and to build a better future for all.

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College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Dr. Katrina Adams, the Gallagher Assistant Professor in the Department of Biological Sciences, earned her B.S. in biochemistry and cell biology at the University of California, San Diego. She then went on to earn her Ph.D. in molecular biology at the University of California, Los Angeles in 2014. Continuing her research in developmental neurobiology, Dr. Adams completed her postdoctoral fellowship at the Center for Neuroscience Research, Children's Research Institute at the Children's National Hospital in Washington, DC, from 2015 to 2022, before accepting her current position at the University of Notre Dame. Her laboratory focuses on investigating signaling pathways that regulate endogenous neural stem cells and progenitor cells in the developing adult brain and how these signaling pathways are altered from disease or injury to the brain, specifically demyelination. Dr. Adams hopes to identify new targets that can be used or

negative signaling pathways that can be targeted to promote more efficient repair. The Adams Lab is currently looking to recruit more members.

Author: Alura D'Souza

Dr. Natasha Dobrinen, full professor in the Department of Mathematics, earned her B.A. in mathematics at the University of California, Berkeley. During her time there, she graduated with high honors and completed a thesis on The Prime Number Theorem. She went on to earn her Ph.D. from the University of Minnesota, during which she concentrated on Boolean algebra. After serving as the NSF VIGRE Chowla Postdoctoral Research Assistant Professor from 2001 to 2004, Dr. Dobrinen worked as a FWF Postdoctoral Fellow at the Kurt Goedel Research Center for Mathematical Logic at the University of Vienna, Austria, from 2004 to 2007. While an assistant professor at the University of Denver in the following year, Dr. Dobrinen founded the BLAST Conference Series, which focused on Boolean algebras, lattices, universal algebra, set theory, and point-free topology. Since its inception

in 2008, this conference series has taken place at seven different universities throughout the Mountain and Midwest regions. More recently, Dr. Dobrinen has expanded her research to include Ramsey theory of infinite structures and the structures of compact spaces while continuing to investigate the applications of set-theoretic methods in the analysis of these phenomena. Beyond her work, Dr. Dobrinen credits her relationship with God as the most important factor that drives her to continue to do research within the field of mathematics; she attributes her inspiration, her journey, and her successes to an innate desire to further understand God's creation. Overall, Dr. Dobrinen continues to pursue her personal and professional interests at the University of Notre Dame.

Author: Quinn Deitch

Dr. Kaiyu Fu, assistant professor in the Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry, began his education in China where he earned his B.E. in polymer science and engineering at Sichuan University in 2011 and his M.S. in polymer chemistry at Fudan University in 2014. After earning his Ph.D. in chemistry at the University of Notre Dame in 2018, Dr. Fu accepted a position as a postdoctoral researcher at Stanford University before returning to Notre Dame to become an assistant professor in 2022. His research currently focuses on making a blood-soluble biomimicking film that acts as a nutrient-measuring device; he originally derived inspiration from diabetes glucose measuring devices. He takes a special interest in the ability to combine all of his knowledge and interests as opposed to focusing solely on one discipline. For example, the device he is working on combines his knowledge and interests in engineering with chemistry and medicine. Outside of research, he enjoys

photography, specifically of the Golden Dome and how it contrasts its surroundings. He has also loved nature and art since childhood, growing up in a city where creativity, appreciating natural surroundings, and grounding oneself was fundamental to being human.

Author: Hanani Ndebele

College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Dr. Yuefeng Han, assistant professor of applied and computational mathematics and statistics, earned his B.S. in mathematics from Zhejiang University. Dr. Han then went on to receive both his M.Sc. and Ph.D. in statistics from the University of Chicago. After receiving his Ph.D., Dr. Han completed his postdoctoral research at Rutgers University.

His research interests include many multifaceted aspects of statistics but specifically big data analysis, high-dimensional statistics, statistical machine learning, tensor data analysis, and time series analysis. In 2016, Dr. Han was awarded the Consulting Award and Senior Consultant from University of Chicago, and he received a fellowship from the same school for 2014–18.

Author: Austin Dungan

Dr. Dafei Jin is an associate professor in the Notre Dame Department of Physics and Astronomy. Dr. Jin grew up in Nanjing, China, and developed an interest in math and physics at an early age. He completed his undergraduate degree at Nanjing University, studying and conducting research in physics. He then completed his Ph.D. at Brown University in 2012, where he furthered his scientific knowledge through research in low temperature physics. Dr. Jin pursued his postdoctoral research at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and the University of California, Berkeley, where he concentrated on nanoengineering.

His educational experiences well prepared him for his work at Argonne National Laboratory, where he studied quantum information science and published several papers on topics such as single-electron quantum systems and optomechanics. At the Argonne National Laboratory, Dr. Jin developed a quantum bit (or qubit) by manipulating single electrons and solid neon. He and his team found that the qubit that they developed had a more efficient quantum lifetime than other existing qubits.

In September 2022, Dr. Jin began his research at the University of Notre Dame. His research approach is multidisciplinary, ranging from quantum information science to condensed matter physics. His research in quantum information science relates to his continued development of the qubit, which will be used for further quantum networking and computing. Dr. Jin's research in quantum material science involves the study of exotic properties of material, such as superconnectivity, and he manipulates matter such as topological material, or material that is robust to environmental noise. Dr. Jin's research has several potential outcomes, one being the ability to generate a better quantum computer, and in this way discover new functional materials. He advises students who are eager to pursue his line of research to focus on understanding overarching concepts and to not shy away from scientific hypotheses that may seem unorthodox.

Dr. Jin enjoys his research because he finds purpose in providing experimental evidence for theoretical ideas and likes to collaborate with the members of his lab. He currently teaches an undergraduate engineering course, as well as a more specialized quantum materials and devices course for physics graduate students. Outside of the classroom, Dr. Jin enjoys spending time with his family. Additionally, he appreciates nature and has traveled to many United States national parks and several other countries such as Canada, Mexico, China, and the Netherlands.

Author: Julia Marine

College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Dr. Marc Osherson, is an assistant professor in the Department of Physics currently working on the Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) collaboration in conjunction with the European Organization for Nuclear Research. Dr. Osherson earned his B.S. in physics at Princeton in 2010 and his Ph.D. at Johns Hopkins in 2016, and completed a postdoctoral fellowship at Rutgers (2022). In December 2022, Dr. Osherson joined the Notre Dame faculty. Dr. Osherson has a deep interest in particle physics, which began during his undergraduate research into dark matter at Princeton. He transitioned to researching particle physics using colliders during his graduate and postgraduate studies. Dr. Osherson's current project as a CMS collaborator seeks to gain greater understanding of the fundamental components of matter, namely the Higgs boson, using the Large Hadron

Collider. Consistent with the goals of the CMS collaboration, Dr. Osherson hopes to discover the existence of additional elementary particles within the Standard Model of particle physics. When outside of the lab, Dr. Osherson enjoys hiking, spending time with family, and teaching his Newfoundland puppy Morgan new tricks.

Author: Brett McLaughlin

Dr. Petr Stepanov, assistant professor in the Department of Physics and Astronomy, earned both his B.Sc. and M.Sc. in applied physics and mathematics at the Moscow Institute of Physics and Technology. He then went on to attend graduate school at the University of California, Riverside from 2012 to 2016 and received his Ph.D. in physics at Ohio State University in 2018. Dr. Stepanov spent his postdoctoral appointment at the Institute of Photonic Sciences in Barcelona, Spain, from 2018 to 2023, studying both superconductivity and orbital magnetism in magic angle twisted bilayer graphene, in addition to photocurrent nanoscopy and near-field optics, before accepting his current position at the University of Notre Dame to continue his work with cryogenic near-field optics in moiré materials. The Stepanov Lab focuses on two-dimensional materials and conducts near-field optical studies

on those materials. The projects in his laboratory center on studying and understanding emergent quantum phases using unique and novel optical methods to gain a greater understanding of the microscopic mechanisms governing quantum phenomena. The Stepanov Lab is currently looking to recruit more members. Outside of the lab and classroom, Dr. Stepanov enjoys reading books about quantum physics and popular science.

Author: Alura D'Souza

Dr. Julián Torres-Dowdall, assistant professor of ecology and evolutionary biology, hails from Argentina and earned his undergraduate degree at the University of Tucumán. Dr. Torres-Dowdall has always been curious about the natural world, but his interest in biology solidified during his undergraduate years when he realized that he enjoyed learning about evolutionary topics and contributing to the growing collective of biological research. During this time, he wrote a thesis regarding the biodiversity of different bird species within Tucumán's botanical gardens and illustrated a book of the birds that he observed. Dr. Torres-Dowdall continued his education at the National University of Córdoba, where he pursued a master's program in wildlife management. Following this experience, Dr. Torres-Dowdall moved to the United States with a Fulbright Fellowship to Colorado State

University. Here, his research focus shifted from birds to fish, finding that fish were a more convenient scientific model upon which to conduct experiments. Additionally, he became interested in studying evolution at the molecular level instead of the organismal level to better understand how phenotypes in fish evolve. For postdoctoral research, he worked at the University of Konstanz, Germany, beginning his investigation into the molecular evolution of vision in fish.

Dr. Torres-Dowdall began his research at the University of Notre Dame during the 2022 fall semester. Using fish, he continues to investigate the evolutionary mechanisms of vision, aiming to address this trait from the molecular level to the community level. He also researches life history strategies in fish that live in high and low latitudes in order to better understand how these species have adapted to different environmental conditions. Dr. Torres-Dowdall's research has many potential outcomes, one being its ability to inform our understanding of abnormal vision phenotypes, information that could affect our understanding of human health. He advises students who would like to pursue his line of research to have a passion for a particular research question, but also to be open to other scientific systems.

Author: Julia Marine

College of Science Faculty Spotlights

Dr. Nicholas Ramsey, assistant professor in the Department of Mathematics, earned his B.A. from the University of Chicago in 2012. He went on to complete his master's degree in France at Université Paris Diderot and his Ph.D. from the University of California, Berkeley in 2018. Dr. Ramsey began his academic career studying philosophy, and it wasn't until he took a logic class that he became enthralled by the world of mathematics and began seeking more knowledge in the sector. He moved to Paris for his master's degree knowing almost no French at all, but thankfully mathematics in French was just accentuated English words. After his time in France he continued his education at the University of California-Berkeley where he joined the program Group in Logic and the Methodology of Science, which combined his interests in philosophy, mathematics, and

computer science. The interdisciplinary nature of the program not only helped him further himself academically, but it also gave him the ability to connect with other people from different disciplines and backgrounds. In his research as a logician on model theory, he primarily focuses on how meaning gets assigned to expression and formal languages, or simply, how mathematics is possible. This ties into the interests in linguistics that he has had since childhood, which started with Latin. The precision of Latin was fascinating to him, and logic was language in its most pure form—it was what he found most rewarding. Outside of his research and work, he enjoys reading and cooking. He particularly enjoys traveling, as it undoes the small viewing frame in his immediate surroundings and allows him to see more of the world.

Author: Hanani Ndebele

Dr. Changbo Zhu, associate professor of applied and computational mathematics and statistics and fellow of the Lucy Institute for Data & Society, earned both his B.S. and M.S. in mathematics from National University of Singapore. He then went on to receive his Ph.D. in statistics from University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign. After completing his postdoctoral research at University of California, Davis, he accepted a position at the University of Notre Dame in 2022, teaching Statistical Methods in Data Mining and Prediction in the fall and Statistical Computing and Monte Carlo Methods in the spring. Dr. Zhu's research interests focus on the concept of statistical association relationships and creating novel statistical models. In particular, Dr. Zhu focuses on extracting statistical relationships from complex datasets, often those profuse in variables. In one of his numerous publications, he highlights the correlation between the development of children's brains

and their environments, finding that children whose mothers received bachelor's degrees had significantly different brain development than those whose mothers did not. Dr. Zhu's longitudinal studies and new inferential methods prompt the advancement of studies in all domains.

Author: Austin Dungan

Former Head Women's Basketball Coach Muffet McGraw Designates \$10,000 Honorarium to Del Valle Lab for Neurodegenerative Disease Research

SISY CHEN AND EMILY HUNT

In February 2023, former Notre Dame women's basketball coach Muffet McGraw was honored with the NCAA 2023 Pat Summitt Award. As an honoree, McGraw has designated a \$10,000 honorarium toward the lab of Dr. Juan Del Valle at the University of Notre Dame, which is working on developing disease-modifying drugs and therapies to slow the progression of neurodegenerative diseases. McGraw chose the Del Valle Lab specifically for its research focus on molecules designed to address a protein called Tau, which is known to be a driver of nearly 40 neurodegenerative diseases collectively termed tauopathies.

(Above) Members of the Del Valle Lab with Muffet McGraw.

The researchers of the Del Valle Lab are broadly interested in harnessing the power of organic chemistry to address contemporary challenges in drug discovery and biomolecular recognition. The study of constrained peptides targeting protein-protein interactions, the synthesis and SAR of non-ribosomal peptide natural products, and modulators of ER stress response are key areas of focus for the lab.

Del Valle and his team of graduate and postdoctoral researchers, known as "Team Tau," are working to create molecules that bind to misfolded tau proteins to hinder their propagation and prevent the toxic fiber buildup that leads to neurodegenerative diseases. McGraw presented the lab with the \$10,000 check at McCourtney Hall—where the Del Valle Lab primarily conducts its research.

McGraw wanted to fund Alzheimer's-specific research in honor of Pat Summitt—the award's namesake and Naismith Memorial Basketball Hall of Fame Tennessee Lady Vols basketball coach. Summitt had died from early-onset Alzheimer's in 2016.

McGraw hopes this research will ultimately lead to a cure for Alzheimer's and other neurodegenerative diseases.

McCourtney Hall is the first interdisciplinary research building dedicated to collaborative research at the crossroads of science and engineering. Del Valle noted that federal agencies tend to be conservative toward "high-risk" research projects like his own. However, this honorarium will play an important role in supporting the lab's innovative research on therapies for people facing neurodegenerative diseases.

McGraw described Summitt as a fierce advocate for female basketball athletes in their game at the time. It's a voice McGraw carries on today, even when it comes to science.

"We'd love to see more women over here in the labs," said McGraw. For McGraw, there is a call to champion women in science, engineering, and other fields that have typically been male-dominated. Two of Del Valle's Team Tau researchers are women—a personal bonus point for her selection of this particular lab, as she admires the value Del Valle places on diversity and inclusion in his work.

The ultimate hope for McGraw is to leave a positive impact on the next generation. "I think we all look at our kids, and we say we want the world to be better when they're older," said McGraw. "[An Alzheimer's cure is] not going to be here in time for my generation, but the next generation—that's what we're hoping for."

GEM Fellowship Awarded to Computational Biology Doctoral Student Studying Neurodegenerative Diseases

GRACE GALFANO

From Isabella Gimon's perspective, "You can't be a good scientist without being a good person." As a passionate researcher committed to improving the lives of others, she need not worry on either account.

A second-year Ph.D. candidate in Dean Santiago Schnell's laboratory, Gimon was recently awarded a GEM Fellowship to continue her research of Alzheimer's disease using computational biology. In particular, she investigates protein aggregation, the process by which misfolded or denatured proteins accumulate in an insoluble clump, sometimes triggering neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease (1). Gimon explains that not all protein aggregation is bad; as such, her research is geared toward distinguishing between the advantageous and deleterious aggregation types. Approaching this question from a computational perspective gives her the freedom to adjust experimental parameters and track changes over time more easily than if she were working in a wet lab. As such, computational biology represents an exciting field with the ability to exceed normal human capabilities.

Gimon's interest in computational biology began when she was a child growing up in Florida. She remembers her mother, a computer scientist, describing her job, saying, "We don't look at the forest; we look at the leaves." In other words, computational scientists are keen observers of detail, utilizing technology to process large amounts of information in a meticulous, efficient manner. Gimon enjoys this aspect of her work, as it allows her to aid experimentalists with their studies. However, Gimon's research transcends computers and code; at the end of the day, her goal is to help people afflicted with debilitating diseases, to reorient science's focus on the people and causes that matter. This issue hits close to home, as Gimon's grandmother was diagnosed with Alzheimer's disease, strengthening her resolve to conduct research in this area. She has worked at MIT and Yale and hopes to continue advancing this cause in the future by working in industry or academia, as well as by donating to charities.

To aspiring scientists and computational researchers, Gimon offers some invaluable advice: "Always cultivate creativity." She explains that "as scientists, we are very fixated on our methodologies, but we progress in science by being creative. I think looking at literature, philosophy, and the humanities can help with this."

(Above) Isabella Gimon.

In addition to thinking imaginatively and taking a multidisciplinary approach, Gimon emphasizes the importance of building a solid foundation for a career in research. Besides taking requisite classes and gaining research experience, she encourages students to identify a mentor and role model who values their personhood as much as their science. She admits that computational biology can be challenging; even after diligent construction of a program, red error messages still find a way of popping up and foiling best-laid plans. As a result, a career in research requires what Gimon calls "tenacious perseverance," as well as a solid support system. To that end, she credits Dean Schnell's mentorship, as well as the Office of Fellowships at Notre Dame, for her recent reception of the GEM Fellowship.

Accidental Discovery of a ‘Raspberry-Shaped’ Nanoparticle May Advance Precision Drug Delivery

JAMES LAZAR

Most cancer drugs never make it to tumors as they simply get “washed out” of the body before they have time to reach and affect the cancer. This often causes variability in the effects of certain drugs and lowers the overall effectiveness of treatment. Nanomedicine, the application of nanotechnology to medicine, is a potential solution to such a problem: microscopic nanoparticles carrying drugs could effectively target tumors and keep drugs in the body to further attack malignant cells. A simple explanation of this effect stems from the fact that nanoparticles are much bigger compared to that of typical drug cells, so they can partition the body in different ways that are oftentimes beneficial to the body when delivering a drug. Hopefully, nanomedicine will be a major contributor to cancer research in the next generation or two, but it is still a new area of medicine that may take decades of fundamental exploration to produce something that will be effective and readily available for practical use.

Dr. Bradley D. Smith, the Emil T. Hofman Professor of Science and director of Notre Dame’s Integrated Imaging Facility, has taken a big step forward with his team in this realm of nanomedicine through an unexpected and accidental discovery. Initially, his lab was trying to find a way to dye tumors to better visualize them in hopes of extracting them through surgery more effectively. They attempted to package dye in mesoporous silica nanoparticles, a safe and established nanoparticle used to target tumors, in hopes of having these dye-filled nanoparticles interact with the tumors to highlight them with dye.

However, there was a problem. The team quickly found that the dye molecules they were trying to inject would not fit in the silica nanoparticles. Consequently, doctoral students Cassandra Shaffer and Canjia Zhai heated the nanoparticle to 80°C to see if they could enlarge the holding capacity of the nanoparticle. After leaving it heated overnight, they wanted to confirm that the dye had fully infused with the nanoparticles, so Shaffer and Zhai enlisted the help of microscopy experts at the Integrated Imaging Facility. What they found was that the dye had indeed become infused, but an unexpected phenomenon had also occurred. The heat caused the silica nanoparticles to change shape. The original particles were solitary spheres lightly dotted with pores, while the new structures were spherical and were composed of smaller dye-filled globules with small openings. These small openings revealed a hollow core inside, which loosely resembled a hollow raspberry-like shape. This was a remarkable discovery because silica typically shows no change even if it is heated up to 500°C, so the fact that they saw a change in its shape at such a low temperature was perplexing.

While they achieved their original goal of injecting dye into the nanoparticles, Dr. Smith wished to explore more of this astonishing discovery. To see if other chemicals could be loaded while remaining active in the altered nanoparticles, doctoral student Jordan Chasteen looked into the possibility of using the nanoparticle as a transport mechanism for a drug called mitoxantrone, a treatment for advanced prostate cancer and acute nonlymphocytic leukemia. After a series of tests, Chasteen confirmed that the cancer drug was still active once loaded into these nanoparticles, and was capable of killing cancer cells.

Beyond its implications in cancer research, this discovery also sheds light on the chemistry of a poorly understood process called biomineralization, by which mineral crystals are deposited in the matrix of living organisms. Some organisms use this process to remodel silica, but the mechanism was not formally understood as there was a presumption that silica must be heated at very high temperatures to cause a change in its structure. However, as Dr. Smith’s lab has discovered, remodeling of the silica nanoparticle can occur at low temperatures, showing that organic chemicals can break silica bonds, which may explain some natural catalytic processes like biomineralization. As Dr. Smith puts it, “Microorganisms have mechanisms that allow them to take sand and remodel it into their shells. And they clearly do it at relatively low temperature using organic molecules. What we have discovered is potentially some of the chemistry behind that process.”

Dr. Smith’s lab has made a discovery with many implications. It particularly has significance in the pharmaceutical industry, as it shows that drugs can be paired with the enlarged silica nanoparticle to produce more effective treatments. However, these implications are still conjecture and the research is preliminary, so Dr. Smith and his team are looking to further this research. This new nanoparticle has the potential to become the foundation for novel research into natural processes like biomineralization, and there are hopes that it will advance the fields of cancer research and nanomedicine together.

Students Return from a Once-in-a-Lifetime Trip to the Galápagos Islands

ANNIE BENN

The Galápagos Islands epitomize the pinnacle of biodiversity and geology intersecting on our planet today. Famous for the evolutionary discoveries of Charles Darwin, the volcanic islands are scattered across either side of the equator in the Pacific off the coast of Ecuador. Evolutionary and geological scholars have flocked to the islands for decades following Darwin's work, and this year during fall break in October, so did Notre Dame undergraduates.

Professors Dr. Gary Lamberti and Dr. Jeremy Fein led a class of fourteen science majors on a ten-day immersion course on the islands. The idea behind this year's excursion stemmed from Dr. Lamberti's first two trips with Dr. Malcom Fraser, who founded the course after a trip with National Geographic. "The first iteration [of this course] was back in 2016," Dr. Lamberti explained. "It was just a way to allow students to see science acting firsthand, and if there's a better learning environment somewhere on this planet, I'd like to know where that is." It's the friendship between Dr. Lamberti and Dr. Fein, and their shared passion for the kind of opportunities presented when visiting the Galápagos, that has kept the course going the past two trips.

One of the major appeals for a trip to these islands is their isolation from humans, which provides a more authentic view of nature at work. "It's an ideal place to see biology and geology interacting with each other, and especially in an isolated environment," Dr. Fein said. "It's relatively unimpacted by people." The islands are also distant from other species, which allows the current inhabitants to thrive and evolve in a more controlled space. However, the maintenance of this isolated environment can be tricky, according to Dr. Lamberti. "There have been several invasive species populating the island over the last few years, such as goats and feral cats," Dr. Lamberti remarked. "There are ongoing efforts from the scientists and park rangers there, as well as the Ecuadorian government, to try and control this."

The differences in topography and geology between the islands makes the biodiversity on these islands unprecedented. Students were able to observe these forces at work, and see firsthand what they had been learning about back in South Bend. "Famously on the Galápagos, some of the finches are evolving even before our eyes," said Dr. Lamberti. "Of course, we can't document that in a week while we are there, but there are plenty of studies that provide evidence for evolution on a scale of even one to two years happening." Evolution normally takes centuries to occur, yet these finches and other animals on the Galápagos shed light into just how fantastic the biology on the islands actually is.

Students were able to experience geology firsthand as well, when they visited the recently active Sierra Negra. "The Galápagos [volcanoes], like the Hawaiian islands, have a range of different activities," Dr. Fein explained. "We hiked up the rim of this volcano and went through several different biological zones until we were above the clouds, and we were able to see fresh geology." The climate of the volcano varied as the students scaled it, with a humid rainforest biome below the clouds, and a dry desert near the peak. This incredible phenomenon was cited by both professors as an instant classic with the students, and rightfully so. They saw exquisite pahoehoe lava flows as well as fresh rock formation from the latest explosion in 2018. "What was really interesting was the fresh geology interacting with these biozones," said Dr. Fein. "And luckily for us, it didn't erupt."

(Above) The students and professors pose in the Galápagos.

The conservation efforts of the park guides and government also struck the students and professors who attended this trip. "The island has really well-managed ecotourism," Dr. Lamberti explained. "Everything is very strictly managed; nobody can even step foot on any of the islands without an Ecuadorian national parks certified guide." Dr. Lamberti stressed just how well-trained these guides were, which spoke to the impressive commitment of the government to preserve the ecological wonder that is the Galápagos. "The management of fisheries and other resources was something we learned about in this course," Dr. Lamberti explained. "There used to be massive exploitation of these fisheries especially, but now everything is done in a much more sustainable fashion." The main source of income for this national park is tourism, but the Ecuadorian government is careful not to overexploit that, in the interest

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Galápagos, *continued*

of preserving the Galápagos. “They have limited numbers of people who are allowed per year, or at a time,” Dr. Fein said. “That sort of long-term thinking is an attitude we should keep in mind.”

Although only fourteen students attended the trip this past October, both professors stressed the importance of what they saw for the greater Notre Dame community. “We often as teachers forget to stress that everything is sort of related on the earth,” Dr. Fein explained. “The biology was so influenced by the geology, and the geology is actually influenced by the biology.” This crossover is something often neglected when professors teach their speciality class, and both professors felt it was something that was incredibly apparent to students who did take this trip. Although the trip had to be constrained in numbers for conservationist reasons, the islands should still be a point of learning for science majors. “We’d like to take every biology, environmental science, and geology student to the Galápagos if we could,” Dr. Lamberti said. “If you can’t get to the Galápagos, and not everybody can, then learn about the Galápagos.”

Exploring the Molecular Basis for Racial Disparities in Cancer Outcomes

BROOKE FRIEDMAN

Cancer is a disease that affects people of all races and ethnicities. However, studies have shown that mortality rates from cancer are disproportionately high among individuals from racially and ethnically diverse backgrounds compared to their white counterparts. While many factors contribute to this disparity, including inadequate access to medical care in low-income communities and lack of trust in healthcare, recent evidence suggests that this disparity may also have a genetic basis.

Isabella (Bella) Allen, a senior undergraduate student studying chemical engineering at the University of Notre Dame, has been investigating this issue under the guidance of Dr. Sophia George at the University of Miami. Specifically, she has been studying the molecular basis for racial disparities in ovarian cancer mortality rates.

Current evidence indicates that high-grade serous ovarian carcinoma, the most common and deadliest ovarian cancer,

originates by the epithelial cells of the fallopian tube rather than the ovaries. Therefore, the George Lab collected tissue samples from the fallopian tubes of thirteen women with mutations in genes that increase the risk of breast and ovarian cancer, such as BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes. The exact mechanism by which these mutations, among others studied, increase breast and ovarian cancer risk is unknown. Further investigation into these mechanisms could be conducted through a technique called single-cell RNA sequencing, which assists medical researchers in understanding an individual’s unique genetic code.

In order to conduct single-cell RNA sequencing on the tissue samples, Allen created a bioinformatics analysis pipeline to analyze the samples and identify different cell clusters with unique transcriptional profiles. She then compared the gene expression patterns of these clusters between different samples, looking for differences among upregulation and downregulation of these genes that might explain this disparity in cancer mortality rates.

Her work is a part of a larger project aimed at understanding the molecular basis for racial disparities in cancer among men and women. Although Allen’s samples were collected from local women in Miami representing a broad range of backgrounds, the lab hopes to generalize its research to women globally. Therefore, this project aims to collect hundreds of tissue samples from people of different races and ethnicities in countries such as the Bahamas, Jamaica, Haiti, Nigeria, and Kenya. To further this aim, Allen was awarded the prestigious Fulbright scholarship, where she intends to continue collecting tissue samples from women in Jamaica. The goal is to create a single-cell atlas of healthy breast, fallopian tube, and prostate cells, which will help researchers understand how cells become cancerous and why different populations have different cancer mortality rates.

(Above) Isabella Allen presenting her research from the George Lab.

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Exploring the Molecular Basis for Racial Disparities in Cancer Outcomes, *continued*

This is an important area of research because it has implications for how cancer is diagnosed, treated, and prevented. Historically, drug treatments for cancer have been tested using primarily Caucasian cell lines, which fail to account for the genetic differences across diverse populations. However, if researchers can identify genetic differences between different populations that affect how they respond to drugs, this could lead to more personalized and effective treatments for cancer.

Overall, Allen's work is a part of a larger effort to understand why individuals from racially and ethnically diverse backgrounds have higher mortality rates from ovarian cancer and to develop strategies for reducing these disparities. By collecting and analyzing samples from diverse populations, the George Lab hopes to identify the genetic factors that contribute to cancer risk and to develop more effective ways of preventing and treating these diseases.

Notre Dame Engineers and Microbiologists at Trinity College Dublin Unite to Improve Cystic Fibrosis Treatment

ALYSSA FIUME

Dr. Robert Nerenberg and Dr. Albert Cerrone are Notre Dame engineers working with Dr. Marta Martins of Trinity College Dublin (TCD) to make meaningful strides in the treatment of cystic fibrosis.

Cystic fibrosis (CF) is a genetic disorder that causes mucus buildup in the lungs, digestive tract, and other areas of the body. While the disease affects many worldwide, Ireland has the highest incidence per capita, and is triple that of the United States.

Current treatments for CF include vibrating vests, which loosen the mucus in the lungs, and antibiotics. Drs. Nerenberg and Cerrone, along with Ph.D. student Yanina Nahum, discovered that low-frequency ultrasounds greatly improve the success of antibiotic treatment for the disease by diminishing the biofilms

that normally decrease its effectiveness. The job now was to figure out on a molecular scale how and why this was working. Dr. Martins, a microbiologist at TCD, provided the team with the expertise needed to grasp at the cellular mechanisms involved in this pathway.

Dr. Nerenberg and Dr. Cerrone describe that the opportunity to work on a multidisciplinary research team has been a largely educational experience, and that working with someone as “energetic and positive” as Dr. Martins has been especially rewarding. Neither Dr. Nerenberg nor Dr. Cerrone have backgrounds in CF research. However, in discovering this mechanism for degrading biofilms with low-frequency ultrasounds, they were able to use their knowledge to make contributions in the treatment of the disease.

The researchers now partner with mentors at the Children's Hospital of Los Angeles in the Cystic Fibrosis Center. This has helped to guide research and establish relevance in the clinical realm. Because the researchers work “far away from the clinical side of things,” this partnership has allowed them to maintain a line of sight into the clinical implications of what they are doing in the lab.

Biofilms are the most common way bacteria grow in the environment, and they are the cause of infection and contamination in many things—prosthetics, implants, water pipes, and much more. This novel combination of low-frequency ultrasound with antimicrobials/antibiotics may have potential applications in many other fields. Dr. Cerrone emphasizes that a large reason for the lab's success is that there are “no egos involved”—and through the combined expertise of all involved, this new approach to CF treatment has the possibility of improving the lives of very many.

Left to right: Rob Nerenberg, Yanina Nahum, and Albert Cerrone.

HBO's *The Last of Us*: Fact or Fiction?

A Deep Dive into Fungal Infections and Dr. Santiago-Tirado's Research

ALEXANDRA NOBLE

Based on the 2013 Playstation video game, HBO's new record-breaking post-apocalyptic drama *The Last of Us* follows society after a mass fungal infection that causes its hosts to transform into zombie-like creatures, collapsing the fabric of American society. Averaging 30.4 million viewers for the first six episodes, the highest number for an HBO series since the eighth season of *Game of Thrones*, this video game adaptation series has captivated viewers, causing us all to ponder the reality of a fungal pandemic of this nature (1). In our (somewhat) post-COVID-19 world, it is now more important than ever to ask ourselves: Are pandemic-causing fungal infections like the one featured in *The Last of Us* fact or fiction?

To break down the science behind *The Last of Us*, Notre Dame assistant professor of biological sciences Dr. Felipe Santiago-Tirado, provided insight into the threat fungal infections pose to the human race while also sharing how his own research with *Cryptococcus neoformans* relates to the type of fungus seen in the series. The fungal apocalypse responsible for the devastation seen in *The Last of Us* is the mind-altering fungus *Cordyceps*. In reality, *Cordyceps* specifically targets insects and cannot infect humans as it cannot survive at human body temperature. However, the series highlights how with climate change, *Cordyceps* could adapt to the warming environment, conferring it the ability to infect human hosts. When asked if the threat of a fungal adaptation similar to the *Cordyceps* apocalypse is a potential reality for the human race, Dr. Santiago-Tirado humorously answered, "Turn humans into zombies? No, that's not going to happen. But fungi—they are a real threat and there are many reasons why." To start, fungi are eukaryotes, which means that they are phylogenetically more closely related to us than bacteria or plants. Because fungi are so closely related to humans, whatever kills fungi will also generate toxicity in healthy human cells. Therefore, creating effective drug therapies to combat fungal infections has puzzled researchers for decades.

Fungal infections notoriously have been ignored by pharmaceutical companies, which has manifested in their high mortality rate each year (~1.6 million deaths per year) as there are few effective and accessible treatments. In fact, a recent report by the CDC highlights the threat that *Candida auris* poses to long-term health centers and nursing homes. The *Annals of Internal Medicine* published that the percentage increase in clinical cases of *C. auris* grew each year, "from a 44% increase in 2019 to a 95% increase in 2021" (2). This highly contagious, multi-resistant fungus exhibits a serious concern to

immunocompromised patients and has the potential to create widespread devastation in human populations due to the lack of effective treatments to combat its infection. Thus, the real threat is not the infection itself, but that humans could become infected by a fungal pathogen and die due to a lack of readily available antifungal therapies. While fungal infections will not turn people into zombies as seen in *The Last of Us*, a situation where billions of people can die from a fungal infection leading to societal collapse presents a spine-chilling possibility.

So how do we attempt to alleviate the threat of a fungal pandemic and create valuable treatments to combat these infections? Dr. Santiago-Tirado and his lab are attempting to answer just that. In his laboratory, Dr. Santiago-Tirado works with two of the most common life-threatening fungi: *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Candida albicans*. He is primarily focused on *C. neoformans*, a neurotropic fungus, meaning that it infects the brain. Although this fungus does not manipulate its host in the same puppeteer-like manner that *Cordyceps* does, it does manifest in symptoms such as headaches, blindness, deafness, and anxiety. Over millennia, fungi similar to *Cordyceps* have evolved to understand and manipulate their host central nervous system. If a fungi of this nature were to infect a human suddenly, it would not know the function of the human central nervous system and thus not possess the same pathogenic capability.

With the limited information available about the pathogenesis and immunology associated with these types of fungal infections, Dr. Santiago-Tirado and his team hope their research provides insight into these gaps in knowledge. More specifically, the Santiago-Tirado Lab has three main research questions it hopes to tackle. First, when a person inhales *C. neoformans* from the environment, it travels to the brain, but it is unknown how this microscopic fungus determines that it needs to make its way to the brain after inhalation.

Furthermore, there are three requirements for a fungus to cause an infection. It has to thrive at human body temperature (37°C), evade or defend itself from the human immune system, and obtain the necessary nutrients for survival. *C. neoformans* remains so catastrophic to human health because macrophages and immune cells recognize it, but are unable to destroy it. Therefore, the Santiago-Tirado Lab is investigating how fungi are able to survive inside immune cells establishing their pathogenesis. Lastly, the lab is examining the large variety of virulence factors unique to *C. neoformans* in hopes of creating

a drug target that is specific to this fungi and hence nontoxic to the healthy human cells. By understanding pathogenesis of this ubiquitous environmental fungus, Notre Dame researchers can shine a much-needed light on this understudied topic, helping to alleviate the threat of fungal infections amongst the human population.

During his introductory microbiology course, Dr. Santiago-Tirado always asks his students on the first day of class what they think of when they hear the term fungal infections. “Students always think about athlete’s foot or ringworm rather than true threats like meningitis-causing fungi,” he disappointingly comments. Sadly enough, it is not just freshman biology students who have disregarded fungal research and infections. It was not until this past year, in October 2022, that the World Health Organization released its first-ever list of health-threatening fungi. That one of the most prominent government agencies focused on global health had not even published a list of priority fungal pathogens reveals a chilling truth about their recognition on the global scale.

Regardless of the feasibility of a zombie apocalypse like the one featured in *The Last of Us*, the series brings necessary attention to the threat fungal infections pose to society and human health. So, thank you, HBO, not only for entertaining us for nine thrilling episodes, but also for communicating to the world that scientific research is exciting, relevant, and important. While *The Last of Us* is not entirely fact, it also is most definitely not fiction.

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(Above) Petri dish with patches of different strains of *Cryptococcus neoformans*.

(Above) A human blood monocyte (colored in pink) containing two *C. neoformans* cells (colored in brown) closely interacting with a brain microendothelial cell (colored in green). *C. neoformans* can use infected immune cells as “Trojan horses” to get inside the brain.

(Above) Dr. Felipe Santiago-Tirado.

For more information on this topic see the following video from the Notre Dame College of Science: <https://youtu.be/OEaagviqI24>

Wastewater-Based Epidemiology on Mpox Detection

CHRISTALIA BARONE

New research was recently published investigating the use of wastewater-based epidemiology to monitor mpox. With research led by Dr. Kyle Bibby, the associate professor of engineering and the Wanzek Collegiate Chair at Notre Dame, and William Chen, a graduate student in the Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering & Earth Sciences, wastewater detection is now a feasible method of locating certain diseases.

Chen, the graduate student in the GERM lab for this project, said that he is “interested in how likely it is to detect any type of pathogen in wastewater.” He had been conducting wastewater testing research on the Zika virus before Dr. Bibby approached him about adding mpox to his analyses. Instead of using wastewater detection on commonly studied diseases such as COVID-19, Chen felt it was necessary to test diseases that are consistently neglected or set to get worse in the future rather than just those with a high outbreak potential. Together, they created a framework database that allows anyone to input their own information about a disease and receive quantitative data that can give a prediction of the likelihood of detecting that disease in wastewater under various circumstances. This database uses the shedding rate in the water of a community to quantify how many cases are present and where they are located. Chen said one of his favorite parts of this research was creating the framework because of how open and accessible it is to anyone and any sort of disease.

Wastewater detection has become an increasingly popular testing method because clinical testing is not accessible everywhere, especially in underserved and underdeveloped areas. Other limitations to clinical testing include the asymptomatic nature of some diseases and the stigmatization surrounding getting tested. Wastewater testing analyzes the water in a community, not the specific infected people, allowing it to bypass some of the challenges associated with clinical testing.

According to the GERM lab, there are many factors that are important for successful detection of diseases. First, there are intrinsic factors, such as the amount of viral DNA shedding of mpox virus. The more shedding that is found in water determines how robust the data will be. Location is also an important factor as it informs flow rate, or how much water is used in a specific area. In turn, flow rate can explain why in some areas diseases are more transmissible than in others. There are also laboratory factors, such as how many replicates were used and how sensitive the methods were. The more replicates and more sensitive the tests, the more likely that the data will show accurate results. When asked about the study’s organization and accuracy, Chen described, “This is important to know because investors will trust your research more, and consequently give you more funding.”

The results from this project may lead to greater communication from public health authorities. Scientists can start utilizing this quantitative data in replacement of clinical data, which will make information about disease prevalence more accessible around the world. Moving forward, the methods used in this study can be applied to not only big diseases, but also smaller, neglected ones such as malaria and tuberculosis. This will benefit people with less resources and privilege, something Chen said he is very passionate about.

Left: Dr. Kily Bibby, Right: William Chen

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The Effects of Kinase Inhibition on the Stability of Biomolecular Condensates, Microtubule-Regulating Structures Composed of Plus-End Tracking Proteins

Noah Abel Baca
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ABSTRACT

Microtubule plus-end tracking proteins (+TIPs) are a family of structurally distinct and evolutionarily conserved proteins that accumulate at and dynamically track the growing ends of cellular microtubules (MTs). +TIPs will generally affect the shape and position of microtubule networks and thus have a significant impact on important cellular processes such as cell division, motility, and morphogenesis. In a recent study, the Goodson lab showed that +TIPs can bind to other +TIPs to form biomolecular condensates, membraneless structures within the cell organized by multivalent interactions between macromolecules. Biomolecular condensates and the +TIPs that compose them can regulate the growth and decay of MT ends and are thus critical modulators of important cellular processes. To examine the regulatory properties of +TIP biomolecular condensates, the Goodson laboratory is using drug treatment to inactivate kinases that are predicted to control the activation or inactivation of known +TIPs. In this subproject, the effects of varying concentrations of the compounds wortmannin and SB216763 were tested in cells that overexpress the plus-end tracking protein CLIP-170. So far, four wortmannin experiments and one SB216763 trial, each utilizing tissue culture, transfection, drug treatment, immunofluorescence, and cell imaging, have taken place. Because of varied technical difficulties, images were successfully generated for the fourth wortmannin experiment only. Drug experimentation studies are ongoing, with the goal of developing a comprehensive model that relates kinase inhibition, condensate formation, and MT growth.

INTRODUCTION

The microtubule (MT) network of the eukaryotic cell consists of microscopic polymers of α and β tubulin dimers that can assemble and disassemble at their two ends. Microtubules contribute to the cellular cytoskeleton and are essential for processes such as cell replication (1). Complex cellular machinery is necessary to regulate the behavior and dynamics of these polymers, which in turn regulate the size and shape of the network. Regulatory elements include microtubule plus-end tracking proteins (+TIPs), a family of structurally distinct and evolutionarily conserved proteins that accumulate at and dynamically regulate the growing end of cellular MTs. Although

distinct, plus-end tracking proteins share several common protein modular domains and motifs. These include intrinsically unfolded domains (often Ser-rich), coiled-coil domains, and C-terminal acidic-aromatic motifs (2).

The functions of +TIPs are diverse and specialized. For example, the +TIP protein CLIP-170 (also known as restin) binds to the plus end of microtubule tips and can promote the growth and bundling of MT polymers (3). Compare this to the +TIP protein KIF2C (MCAK), which is a microtubule depolymerizer that functions in chromosome segregation during mitosis (4). The two +TIPs mentioned display associated yet firmly distinct functions; this observation supports the contention that each +TIP acts in a highly specific cellular context to perform a specialized task. About 20 different groups of +TIPs have been discovered thus far (5). In general, +TIPs affect the shape and position of microtubule networks and have a significant impact on important cellular processes such as division, motility, and tissue development (6). However, many of the mechanisms that regulate these processes are not fully understood.

One puzzling aspect of +TIPs is that many +TIPs bind to other +TIPs (7). Recently, the Goodson lab has shown that these interactions can cause the +TIPs to self-assemble into biomolecular condensates, membraneless compartments within cells established via liquid-liquid phase separation (LLPS) (7). This observation has been confirmed by other more recent publications (8). Liquid-liquid phase separation occurs when weak multivalent macromolecule interactions drive the transition of certain proteins into another phase. Because weak interactions between macromolecules are stronger than macromolecule-water interactions, solvent conditions are poor, and the molecules separate into their own distinct layer (9). LLPS can therefore create gradients of macromolecules that influence the position and concentration of other molecules within the droplets (7).

Biomolecular condensates have thusly been proposed to increase the rate of biochemical reactions within the cell. Co-localization of reactants increases the probability that any two molecules A and B will randomly collide in space, as the space they are confined to is reduced in size. In the case of +TIP-+TIP associations, the binding of complementary domains of +TIPs might be expected to stabilize a condensate by lowering the Gibbs free energy of the system, inducing LLPS and subsequent co-localization. If these +TIPs promote interactions between the tubulin subunits in MT tips, MT growth reactions would be predicted to operate at faster rates.

While the Goodson lab has recently shown that a network of +TIPs can form condensates, and that +TIP-overexpression-induced condensates in cells have properties similar to native +TIP networks localized at the plus-end of MTs, the mechanisms by which these networks dynamically regulate MT length and directionality remain undefined. Moreover, the question of whether native +TIP networks are actually biomolecular condensates remains unresolved. As a result, the role

of biomolecular condensates in the regulation of MT function has emerged as an important area of novel research in cell biology. This question may also have implications for human health: While the exact mechanisms are unknown, defective condensates assembled from MT-binding proteins have indeed been implicated in some neurodegenerative illnesses such as Alzheimer's (9, 10).

One way to begin to address these questions about +TIP condensates is to investigate the mechanisms by which the interactions that lead to +TIP condensates are regulated, e.g., by kinases and phosphatases. In biochemistry, a kinase is an enzyme that "catalyzes the phosphorylation of certain molecules by ATP" (11). Antagonistically, a phosphatase will remove a phosphate group from these molecules. Classically, the addition of a phosphoryl group to a protein will activate/inactivate the protein in question. For example, once added to a protein, strong negative charges of the phosphoryl group can produce unfavorable interactions between the protein and other particles, blocking binding (12). Alternatively, these charges could promote a different interaction.

Phosphorylation sites at Serine, Threonine, and Tyrosine residues within the amino acid sequences of certain +TIPs have been identified using a combination of previous research (e.g., mass spectrometry) and gene sequence comparison to predicted phosphorylation site sequences (13). Protein kinases and phosphatases are expected to regulate +TIPs via these phosphorylation site sequences. +TIP kinases and phosphatases are therefore potential targets of experimental manipulation themselves. Consistent with this idea, Serine 156 of the +TIP EB1 (a +TIP that promotes MT polymerization and is defective in endometrial cancer (14)) is phosphorylated by GSK3, which was experimentally inhibited by the drug wortmannin (15). However, the identity of the specific kinases and phosphatases that regulate these proteins is for the most part poorly explored.

To improve our understanding of +TIP regulation, we are using droplets induced by CLIP-170 overexpression (7) as a tool. Briefly, if a phosphorylation event regulates interaction between +TIPs, we would predict that a drug that inhibits the relevant kinase or phosphatase (and thus effects the level of phosphorylation) would change the size or dynamics of the droplets. This would provide evidence that we can control the formation of biomolecular condensates through their own regulation. For example, if a kinase inhibitor prevents the formation of droplets, it would suggest that kinase activity is necessary for droplet formation and/or maintenance. Conversely, if a kinase inhibitor promotes the formation of a droplet, it is likely that the kinase being tested normally inhibits the formation of a droplet.

Overall, I hypothesize that certain drugs can be used to disrupt or enhance the activity of specific +TIP kinases and phosphatases and thus can disrupt or enhance condensate formation within the eukaryotic cell. This information will have several

applications. First, these disruptions can be used to determine which kinases and phosphatases are involved with the +TIPs under examination. They can also provide a greater ability to manipulate these condensates for future studies. More specifically, we hope to find drugs to stabilize the condensates and then use them for biochemical characterization of the condensates. Future lab experiments will involve the use of a "BioID protein labeling" mechanism. In this experiment, a CLIP170-BioID fusion protein will be created. BioID can biotinylate proteins in its local vicinity; thus, when attached to CLIP170, BioID will label proteins that surround and interact with CLIP170—namely, the local "patch" (i.e., condensate) proteins.

In this report, I describe the experimental strategy and results of the experiments that seek to respond to the hypotheses above. Drug treatment and fixation, immunofluorescence, cell imaging, and image processing were performed to test the effects of several kinase-inhibiting drugs on the formation of biomolecular condensates within NIH3T3 mouse fibroblast cells. Thus far, the data are inconclusive. However, we hope that further experiments will provide conclusive evidence that the regulation of biomolecular condensates is controlled by kinase and phosphatase activity, and/or that the disruption of certain +TIPs will impede the formation of biomolecular condensates and associated droplets surrounding MT plus-ends.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

NIH3T3 mouse embryonic fibroblast cells were removed from liquid nitrogen storage, thawed, and plated with 10 ml 10% FBS in DMEM with L-glutamine. Tissue culture using a 1:40 dilution was performed every 3–4 days to retain 60–70% confluency for transfection. Before transfection, a hematocytometer was used to measure the concentration of detached cells in aspirated media. Cells were diluted into standard cell growth media containing FBS to the desired concentration (typically ~2E5 cells per 2 ml) and added to 4–5 wells of a 6-well plate, each containing glass coverslips. The number of wells used was based on the number of concentrations tested for a given experiment. After 24 hours, transfection with p72 DNA plasmid that expresses CLIP-170 under control of the CMV promoter (16) (347.4 ng/μl) was performed in order to induce CLIP-170 overexpression. The transfected cells were grown for 24 hours during which time the CLIP-170 transfected cells often formed large biomolecular condensates that contain CLIP-170 and other +TIP proteins (7). Wells were then treated with a particular drug at varying concentrations related to the IC50 of the drug. After one hour, the glass coverslips were removed and immunofluorescence staining (using both methanol and PFA protocols) was carried out using the following primary and secondary antibodies: 1° CLIP-170 anti-Xenopus (1:500) & 2° Alexa Fluor™ 488 anti-rabbit (1:1000) (green) from ThermoFisher, 1° 1A2 tubulin anti-mouse (1:1000) & 2° Cy3 anti-mouse (1:400) (red). DAPI fluorophore was added for nuclear staining. Coverslips were mounted and imaged using a Nikon Eclipse TE2000 Inverted Microscope at standardized exposures and light levels.

Image processing was completed using the processing software ImageJ. In order to produce consistent, comparable images, the brightness and contrast minimum and maximum settings were set to the same value across all image types (e.g., the same values for all DAPI stain images). In the generated images below, min. and max. were set to 30 and 2000 for the tubulin sets, 30 and 700 for the CLIP-170 sets, and 50 and 200 for DAPI. These values were chosen with respect to the clarity of the majority of images. Without these standardizations, comparisons between image sets would be unreasonable.

RESULTS

In this report, we sought to examine the effects of the kinase inhibitors wortmannin and SB216763 treatment on the biomolecular condensates within CLIP-170 transfected cells. We expected these drugs to be inhibitors of droplet formation, as we chose drugs that blocked the kinases GSK3 and PI3K, which both upregulate +TIP activity. An overview of our experimental approach is as follows. For each drug experiment, mouse tissue culture cells were grown on glass coverslips and transfected with plasmids to overexpress the condensate-forming protein CLIP-170. Transfected cells were treated with one of the drugs, fixed, stained with antibody, and the coverslips with their adherent cells were mounted onto slides. Slides were imaged, and images were organized and processed into Figures 1 and 2.

We have so far produced four image sets corresponding to three different tested concentrations of wortmannin and DMSO (control). We performed five experiments—four wortmannin experiments and one SB216763 trial. The images presented here were sourced from the fourth iteration of the wortmannin experiment; iterations 1–3 were unsuccessful (see Discussion). Similarly, experimentation with the drug SB216763 was unsuccessful, and images from this experiment could not be generated. All cells imaged were NIH3T3 mouse fibroblast cells transfected with plasmid p72 and stained with antibody as described above.

Image sets for cells treated with drug concentrations of 1.5 μM , 6 μM , 12 μM , and 0 μM (DMSO) using a PFA-fixation and preparation protocol are included in this report. For each image set, three arbitrarily chosen and distinct areas of the slide were imaged. Each row in the figure corresponds to one of these areas, and each column corresponds to a different antibody/fluorophore combination that labels a different subcellular structure, with the fourth column representing the merged image. The cell structures labeled by each fluorophore are listed in the heading of the figure.

We expected to see a significant change in condensate morphology after drug treatment. For wortmannin only, this same experiment has been run in the past by other members of the lab. Those earlier experiments had produced dramatic results: In them, the wortmannin treatment caused the condensate to become “starry.” Condensates became localized along the

length of the microtubules and fractured into a multitude of tiny, speck-like patches. Results observed then were significantly different from control (data not shown; these experiments were conducted by my lab mates). This “starriness” pattern was hypothesized to be either 1) wortmannin interfering with CLIP170’s ability to track MTs and/or 2) wortmannin affecting MT stability.

One purpose of our experiment was to verify that the pattern observed in previous experiments still held true. Ultimately, we were unable to reproduce true “starriness” in the experiments reported above: Observed results do not differ significantly from control (Figure 1). We hypothesize that our failure to reproduce these results may result from differences in the drug itself (e.g., due to manufacturing difference and/or drug age) or unintentional differences in the experimental protocol. We can make no definitive conclusions about the effect of our tested drugs on patch formation from the data above. However, it was observed that wortmannin appeared to decrease the density of the tubulin network in the treated cells, especially at higher concentrations (compare Figure 1D, third column, to the third column in panels A, B, and C). Thus, the wortmannin might have had some effect on treated cells, although this effect was not the observation we expected to see. Further investigation is required, and repeated experiments will be necessary, to paint a more cohesive picture of the effect of wortmannin on CLIP-

(a)

170 biomolecular condensates.

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1 (a, b, c, d). NIH3T3 cells transfected with p72 plasmid DNA expressing CLIP-170, treated with 1.5, 6, and 12 μ M wortmannin (as indicated) for one hour, then fixed with PFA and stained with primary and secondary antibody against CLIP-170 and tubulin as indicated (see materials and methods). Each row corresponds to a different area of the same slide (i.e., the same concentration of wortmannin).

DISCUSSION

Experimentation using kinase inhibitors was conducted to investigate the regulation of biomolecular condensates containing microtubule plus-end tracking proteins (+TIPs). The effects of varying concentrations of wortmannin and SB216763 were tested in a line of transfected cells that overexpress the plus-end tracking protein CLIP-170. Wortmannin, a metabolite from the fungi *Penicillium funiculosum*, is a potent PI3K inhibitor with an inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of 5 nM, a measure of the ability of a molecule to inhibit a certain biochemical function. A PI3K inhibitor was selected because PI3K (phosphoinositide-3-kinase) is a strong activator of cell survival and has a broad effect on multiple biochemical pathways that upregulate cell growth. PI3K will catalyze the addition of a phosphoryl group onto phosphatidylinositol, which can activate protein kinase B, upregulating the PI3K/AKT/mTOR

cell growth pathway. This pathway has been found to be overactive in many types of cancer (17). As an anti-cancer drug, we predicted that wortmannin would be able to reduce the rate of condensate/cell growth through modification of PI3K. We further believed that MT growth would be stunted, and that the condensate would form a particularly distinguishable pattern as a result.

Conversely, SB216763, a maleimide derivative, is a potent and selective GSK3 (glycogen synthase kinase) inhibitor that has an IC₅₀ of 34 nM (18). When GSK3 is active, it will deactivate glycogen synthase A, changing it to its inactive B form. Inactivation of GSK3 will promote glycogen synthesis, which is associated with reduced cell growth (18, 19).

Images provide little support for our hypothesis that wortmannin affects patch morphology or dynamics. Compared to control, cells treated with wortmannin do show a reduced density of tubulin networks (compare Figure 1D, column 3, to column 3 of panels A, B, and C). Patch density, however, does not seem to be affected by wortmannin, even in the highest concentrations tested. Differences between wortmannin and control slides are not overly dramatic; localization and image brightness differs in some areas, but not enough to provide evidence of significant condensate change.

Multiple trials were required for wortmannin before a “successful” experiment was performed. In trials 1–3, cells were either 1) not observed, 2) not successfully transfected, or 3) unusable due to time constraints when imaging with GFP (GFP signal decays over time). The lab hypothesized that inadequate plasmid concentration levels could have been liable for the errors causing point 2. SB216763 trials were interrupted due to microscope maintenance problems (the fluorescent lamp ceased functioning). As GFP was used in the SB216763 trials (point 3), our slides had expired by the time the microscope resumed operations.

We undertook this work because we seek to find a drug treatment that can manipulate patch dynamics in a predictable way so that we can use this information to dissect the regulation of +TIP patches and also so that we can use these drugs as tools in biochemical characterization of patch components. To that end, future directions include the repetition of wortmannin and SB216763 trials, as well as experimentation with nocodazole and taxol. These drugs have a less “global” effect than wortmannin (a.k.a., these drugs inhibit fewer biochemical pathways and thus have less downstream effects than wortmannin); therefore, specific cascading effects of kinase inhibition on condensate formation may be easier to elucidate. The lab is also in the process of establishing a “stable cell line” of COS7 monkey kidney tissue cells, wherein cells with a successful transfection event have been continuously selected for on antibiotic plates. This line will provide improved consistency of transfected cells on the slide and will balance the percentage of transfected cells on any given image. This paper provides a solid foundation to support future work on determining the key properties of biomolecular condensates.

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Event-Related Potentials in Emotions Attention: A Literature Review

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INTRODUCTION

This paper reviews and presents a comprehensive and descriptive overview of available literature surrounding the event-related potentials (ERPs) and the event-related oscillations (EROs) implicated in emotion recognition, processing, and attention. Additionally, the indicated and hypothesized effects of and correlations between emotion valence, emotion intensity, and task relevance and relevant ERPs and EROs are also synthesized.

1. Event-Related Potentials

Event-related potentials (ERPs) are electrophysiological responses to sensory, cognitive, and motor stimuli. ERPs can be extracted from electroencephalogram (EEG) data which measures electrical signals from the scalp. These signals may be modulated or attenuated by stimulus type, and experimental designs and may differ significantly across populations depending on sex, gender, emotional intelligence and sensitivity, mental disorders, neurodivergence, etc. ERPs are named and categorized based on valence (positivity / negativity) and time occurrence following an eliciting stimulus, and they have been found to be correlated with specific cognitive processes.

1.1 N170

N170 is a negative component that occurs approximately 170 ms post-stimulus onset, and it is one of the most commonly studied ERPs implicated in emotional processing and recognition. The N170 appears to be attentive to the identification of facial compared to non-facial stimuli (Leppanen et al., 2007) and an increased N170 amplitude is almost always observed with emotional expressions compared to neutral one. However, its function and correlations are highly contented—some studies report a specificity to negative valence, high arousal stimuli like fear and anger (Righart & de Gelder, 2008; Schindler et al., 2020), but other studies contradicted these findings and reject emotion-specificity for N170, showing an absence in amplitude and latency differences between happy, fearful, and angry emotions (van Heijnsbergen et al., 2008; Luo et al., 2010; Dennis et al., 2009). In Eimer et al. (2008), N170 amplitude was affected by emotion expression only when it was attended to during an emotion task rather than during word, letter, and line tasks. Dennis et al. (2009) further noticed that improved attentional maintenance was associated with increased N170 amplitudes. However, regardless of emotion, N170 amplitude is increased by the intensity of the emotion with the amplitudes being greater with greater intensity (Utama et al., 2009).

1.2 P3

P3 (also known as P300) is a positive component occurring

approximately 300 ms post stimulus. This component is often separated into P3a, which correlates with orienting and involuntary shifts in attention, and P3b, which correlates with sustained attention and memory processing. P3 amplitudes are enhanced for emotionally negative stimuli such as fearful and angry expressions compared to happy ones, though all emotional expressions have larger amplitudes than neutral ones, and also for arousing auditory tones (Schupp et al., 2007; Widmann et al., 2018; Schindler & Bublitzky, 2020; Campanella et al., 2010). P3 latency, specifically P3b latency, is further shown to be shorter for happy faces compared to sad ones (Liu et al., 2013; Campanella et al., 2010). However, manic and schizophrenic patients showed reversed trends where P3 amplitudes were decreased and P3b latencies were prolonged positive expressions and reduced for negative ones. (An et al., 2003; Ergen et al., 2008; Ryu et al., 2010), potentially reflecting impaired emotional cognitive and evaluating processes in persons with altered mental states. Campanella et al. (2010) also found that P3b amplitudes were lower in persons with anxious and depressive tendencies compared to a control group. Attention appears to attenuate P3 amplitudes when compared to passive viewing tasks (Schupp, et al., 2007; Meinhardt & Pekrun, 2003).

1.3 LPP

The Late Positive Potential (LPP) component occurs approximately 400 ms post-stimulus onset and persists for a few hundred milliseconds (~600 ms). LPP appears to be sensitive to attention and emotional presence, intensity, and valence. Emotional faces and negative conditions produce larger amplitudes compared to neutral ones (Schindler & Straube, 2020; Mairon et al., 2020). Within emotional faces, fearful faces elicit higher amplitudes compared to neutral faces (Schindler et al., 2020). LPP is also significantly larger for stimuli showing figures compared to scenes (Nordstrom & Weins, 2012) and for target stimuli (Schupp et al., 2006; Choi & Watanuki, 2014; Schindler & Straube 2020; Weins et al., 2011). LPP is attenuated when attention is directed away from negative to neutral stimuli (Hajack et al., 2009; Nordstrom & Weins, 2012), indicating a significant impact of attention on the component. Solomon et al. (2012) found a sex-discriminative LPP difference; girls had larger LPP amplitudes for unpleasant vs. neutral stimuli whereas boys had larger LPP amplitude for pleasant vs. neutral stimuli. LPP differences have been noted across clinical populations as well; Castro et al. (2019) showed that persons with schizophrenia, who display emotion regulation abnormalities, had blunted LPP responses to negative images but did not have a significant reduction for positive or neutral stimuli. LPP was also attenuated in youths with depressive disorders when presented with emotional face stimuli (Grunewald et al., 2019).

1.4 P1 and N1

P1 and N1 are the first positive and negative ERP components to occur, and they can be seen around the 100 ms point after stimulus onset. The role of P1 in emotion and attentional processing is not well understood; some studies have found no clear effect of facial expression on P1 latency and amplitude

(Righart & de Gelder, 2008; Kissler et al., 2009, Schindler et al. 2020). Utama et al. (2009) noted that P1 was associated with detection of emotional stimuli but was not modulated by the intensity or emotion. Other studies have noticed increased P1 amplitudes for negative emotions like fear, anger, and sadness (Lassalle & Itier, 2013; Luo et al., 2010; Dennis et al., 2009). In some instances, P1 latency was decreased for fearful images (van Heijnsbergen et al., 2008). Bar-Haim et al. (2005) noted P1 latency was further decreased when the group shown fearful expressions were highly anxious. The effect of emotion on N1 is also unclear. Luo et al. (2010) found increased N1 amplitudes elicited by fearful faces while González-Villa et al. (2014) found no effect of task or valence. Kissler et al. (2009) found a non-significant amplitude increase elicited by pleasant words rather than neutral or unpleasant words during a reading and counting tasks.

1.5 P2 and N2

P2 and N2 are the positive and negative components that are seen approximately 200 ms after stimulus onset. There appears to be only minor modulation of these components by emotional faces, valence, intensity, or attention. Schindler & Bublatzky (2020) noted an overall lack of P2 modulation by angry, happy, or neutral faces in the studies it analyzed, but González-Villa et al. (2014) saw a significantly larger P2 factor score for negative words compared to positive ones. P2 latency was faster and its amplitude larger when observing highly anxious individuals as well (Bar-Haim et al., 2005). It has been suggested that the P2 amplitude increases with emotional presence when attended (Kanske et al., 2011). Liu et al. (2013) found that happy faces elicited a more negative N2 component but had no effect on latency, but it has also been seen that N2 amplitudes increase only when emotional cues are task relevant or presented in a congruent condition (González-Villa et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2019).

1.6 EPN and VPP

The Early Posterior Negativity (EPN) component occurs around 200–300 ms following stimulus onset while the Vertex Positive Potential (VPP) component is seen around 170 ms. Schupp et al. (2006) suggests that EPN is modulated by picture content (people vs. objects), picture arousal (low vs. high), and type (scattered vs. single item), but it is related to the perception determining selective attention and not reflective of emotional arousal. For picture content, EPN has been noted to be increased by tasks involving humans and faces over objects (Schindler et al., 2020; Nordstrom & Wiens, 2021). EPN amplitude was increased for all emotional pictures and tasks over neutral ones (Schindler & Bublatzky, 2020; Kissler et al., 2009; Schindler et al., 2020), though there were sometimes larger responses to negative valence emotions like anger and fear. Inattention may attenuate or entirely eliminate EPN if the evoking negative pictures become task-irrelevant (Wiens et al., 2011; Nordstrom & Wiens, 2012). Emotion has a significant effect on quickening VPP latency, especially for fearful expressions, but there was no amplitude difference between emotions (van Heijnsbergen et al., 2008; Luo et al., 2010).

2. Event-Related Oscillations

Event-related oscillations are neural oscillatory activities that reflect the synchronicity of neuronal firings in response to an eliciting stimulus. Different oscillatory bands and their activity, power, and specific frequencies are associated with different cognitive processes and mechanisms and can be affected by a variety of factors including altered mental states and stimuli content.

2.1 Gamma Band

The gamma band ranges from 30 Hz to 100 Hz, though it is often split into a lower band (30–50/60 Hz) and a higher band (50/60–100 Hz). Most literature confirms a correlation between gamma band activity (GBA), power, and synchronization with emotional processing, with an affinity for negative conditions; emotional stimuli (fear and anger) are correlated with increased GBA and synchronization (Matsumoto et al., 2006), especially in negative conditions (Balconi & Lucchiari, 2008; Li et al., 2015). GBA appears to be altered in persons with neurodivergence; patients with alexithymia, an umbrella term for the tendency to have difficulty expressing, connecting with, or recognizing emotions usually within oneself, showed no difference in gamma band responses and little synchronization when viewing negative vs. neutral pictures (Matsumoto et al., 2006). Additionally, children with ADHD were found to have significantly less GBA during facial emotion recognition tasks (specifically for anger and happiness) than the control group in Sarraf Ravazi et al. (2017).

2.2 Alpha and Beta Bands

Alpha (8–13 Hz) and beta bands (15–30 Hz) are thought to be tied to directed and passive attention. Alpha and beta band powers are often decreased when viewing high arousal stimuli compared to neutral ones, especially in the cortical visual areas. Alpha and beta event-related desynchronization (EDR) is stronger for high arousal (e.g., erotic pictures) and negative conditions (e.g., angry faces) compared to both positive or neutral conditions (Guntekin & Basar, 2007; Schubring & Schupp, 2019; Kim et al., 2021). Schubring & Schupp (2019) also found increased EDR for target stimuli compared to non-target stimuli during an active viewing task. It is hypothesized that this reflects enhanced attentional information processing due to alpha-band oscillation being representative of suppressing task-irrelevant information and beta-band activity being related to mirror neuron activity. However, Balconi & Pozzoli (2008) found no modulation of alpha band power by emotion vs. neutral stimuli.

2.3 Delta and Theta Bands

Delta (0–4 Hz) and theta (3–7 Hz) activity seems to show shows sensitivity to emotion over neutral expressions (Balconi & Pozzoli, 2008), and angry faces have evoked significantly higher delta and theta synchronization (Knyazev et al., 2009; Diao et al., 2017). Diao et al. (2017) and Balconi & Pozzoli (2008) observed correlations between N2/N2pc component differences for angry over happy faces and stronger theta oscillatory activity in the negative condition. When observing band activity in patients with schizophrenia, the schizophrenic

group had significantly lower evoked delta band responses (Ergen et al., 2008) and significantly lower theta band responses (Ramos-Loyo et al., 2009).

CONCLUSION

The association and effects of emotion and attention on ERPs and EROs is still a novel field, and more information is needed to understand these exact relationships. According to the previous literature, it may be proposed that the LPP and P3 components are the most sensitive to differences in emotion presentation, valence, and intensity—amplitudes were increased most often with high arousal, negative emotions like fear and anger compared to happy or neutral ones. They also appear to be modulated by attention to the stimuli.

On the other hand, the N170 component generally seems to lack the same emotional discrimination, and the P1, N2, P2, and N2 components only have slight modulations by emotion type and presentation but are usually more associated with the detection of emotion. The gamma band is more closely correlated with emotion detection and processing than the other bands, and it shows increased activity and synchronization with negative conditions. Furthermore, persons with alexithymia or ADHD have been shown to have blunted gamma responses, which may be indicative of difficulties labeling or expressing emotions.

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Coping with COVID-19: The Relationship of Interpersonal Mindfulness and Parent Adjustment to the Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has introduced momentous changes to every aspect of families' lives, leaving parents and children alike to adapt to a new normal. One of the ways that parents sustained mental wellness is through the practice of mindfulness, which involves the focusing of one's attention on what one is presently experiencing in an open and accepting manner. Daily mindfulness practices have an extensive span of psychological benefits, and studies on mindful parenting have shown positive outcomes in both parental well-being and child behavior. This study seeks to investigate how parents cope with the added challenges associated with the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, it considers whether practices of interpersonal mindfulness in parenting are associated with parent coping with the pandemic. The Parenting in the Pandemic Study sample consisted of 217 caregivers, and it was open to any parent in the US with at least one child aged 4–12. The present study used the Interpersonal Mindfulness in Parenting Scale and the Coping with Pandemic Parenting author-developed question to examine these relationships. We used a regression analysis to measure associations between interpersonal mindfulness and parent adjustment to the pandemic. This study revealed a positive relationship between mindful parenting and perceived coping with COVID-19, supporting the benefits of mindful parenting practices as a potential mediating mechanism for parental stress.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, parents and children alike struggled to adapt to a new normal. One of the more significant life adjustments made compulsory by the pandemic was the extensive closure of schools. Schools are regularly regarded as a safe space where parents can rely on teachers to facilitate their children's education and socialization (Kelly, 2020). Fifty-seven million students and their families were affected across the United States when all K–12 schools were shut down in March of 2020 (Donohue & Miller, 2020). Parents had to find ways to cope with the added stressors and psychological issues that had been brought about by school closures and children's confinement at home (Fegert et al., 2020; Halvorsen et al., 2020). Parents across the country were tasked with adjusting their own daily lives as well as accommodating the changes in their children's lives.

These changes brought about a multitude of new pressures for parents with school-aged children, such as financial strain, home crowding, routine changes, and increased caregiving

burden (Prime, Wade & Browne, 2020). Parents attended to responsibilities of childcare and nurturing alone that generally are a collaborative effort along with other adults. For those whose children are in school, this included teachers. Even though some educators provided remote instruction as well as synchronous learning (Garbe et al., 2020), they no longer had a physical presence for the child in their education and everyday lives. As education across the country shifted to a remote format, the schooling of children took place in the home. Thus, parents had to take on more of the responsibilities previously carried by school staff (Halvorsen et al., 2020).

Employed parents had to manage adjustments in their workplaces while simultaneously handling added responsibilities in regard to childcare. Some parents lost their jobs, causing additional financial strain and other burdens (Fegert et al., 2020). Many companies transitioned to remote platforms during the pandemic, forcing employees to learn on the fly how to do their jobs from home, as well as how to cope with the competing demands of their work and their home life (Swit, 2022). Parents who had to continue to work in essential worker positions were at an elevated risk of contracting COVID-19 (Brown et al., 2020). All of these employment circumstances caused demands that could result in elevated stress within the home. The scope of this clash of job and parenting responsibilities was certainly unprecedented (Swit, 2022).

Multiple studies have shown a significant increase in parenting stress throughout the pandemic (Hiraoka & Tomoda, 2020; Brown et al., 2020; Cluver et al., 2020). Parenting stress has been found to be correlated with increased negative outcomes for both children and parents (Spinelli et al., 2020; Masarik & Conger, 2017). During the pandemic, parents spent more time in the everyday caregiving of their children and had fewer opportunities to engage in personal coping with stressors in their lives as a result. The absence of help with childcare, which may normally have served as a respite for parents, likely caused another notable interference to the habitual family routines (Cluver et al., 2020). They could no longer access activities or places that may have served as a well-being booster before the lockdown, including parks, churches, shopping malls, restaurants, and gyms, among other leisure activities (Swit, 2022). A major consequence of this lockdown was the disruption of family cohesion and individual well-being (Fegert et al., 2020). More time together as a family unit does not necessarily mean productive, quality time (Roxburgh, 2006). Isolation restrictions separated people from their normal social networks, cultivating feelings of solitariness, while also adding to the demand of relationships within the household (Spinelli et al., 2020). The pressures of parenting during the pandemic may have been additionally exacerbated for single parents, particularly due to the imposed restrictions on additional caregiver drop-ins and availability of supplementary support (Sorkkila & Aunola, 2020).

Research on the COVID-19 pandemic has yet to address the psychological implications on family dynamics and parent emotional exhaustion (Giusti et al., 2020). This present study

is important in understanding these impacts on families and evaluating a possible coping mechanism for parents. One of the ways that parents tried to sustain mental wellness during the pandemic was through the practice of mindfulness (Johnson, 2020). Mindfulness is a present moment awareness of one's thoughts, emotions, sensations, and environment (Zhang et al., 2021). Mindfulness involves the focusing of one's attention on what one is presently experiencing in an open and accepting manner (Kabat-Zinn, 2003). Mindfulness has been found to be correlated with greater self-efficacy, coping, and emotion regulation (Keng et al, 2011).

Mindful parenting is defined as intentionally, presently, and non-judgmentally paying attention to your child (Kabat-Zinn, 2009). Mindfulness in parenting is reflected through parent-child interactions, especially in the attitude of compassion and acceptance that is held in these interactions. Non-judgmental, present-moment awareness increases a parent's capacity for empathetic concern and sharing the child's perspective (Block-Learner et al., 2007). Studies on mindful parenting have shown positive outcomes in both parental well-being and child behavior (Ahemaitijiang et al., 2021). In addition, mindfulness in parenting can promote growth in emotional regulation and adaptive appraisal (Bögels et al., 2010). These skills can improve reactionary responses to tense instances, alleviating strain within the parent-child relationship.

Dimensions of Mindful Parenting	Parenting Behaviors Promoted through Mindful Parenting	Positive Outcomes in Parent-Child Relationships
Emotional awareness of self and child	Elevated responsiveness to self's and child's needs	Decreased dismissiveness of emotions, and increased sense of trust and safety
Listening with full attention	Accurate perception of child's behavioral cues and verbal communication	Improved communication between parent-child dyad
Nonjudgemental acceptance of self and child	Realistic expectations for child's traits and parent efficacy	Grown appreciation and respect for child's traits and parent efficacy
Compassion for self and child	Greater affection within the parent-child relationship	Decreased negative affect within the relationship, and more forgiving of parenting efforts
Self-regulation in the parenting relationship	Parenting in accordance with personal goals and values	Decreased reactive disciplinary action and negative affect within dyad

Figure 1: Mindful Parenting in Practice. This diagram shows the positive outcomes of mindful parenting in regard to parental well-being, parent-child relationships, and child development when practiced in alignment with the five dimensions of mindful parenting. (Figure adapted from Ahemaitijiang et al., 2021, and Duncan et al., 2009.)

Research conducted prior to the pandemic showed that people who practice mindfulness regularly are better able to cope with elevated levels of stress (Bögels et al., 2010; Potharst et al., 2017; Beer et al., 2013). Mindfulness practices may serve as a buffer against negative impacts of stress on mental and psychological health, both by adjusting stress appraisals and lowering reactivity (Baer et al., 2012; Chiesa & Serretti, 2009). For example, when a parent employs self-regulation, one of the five dimensions of mindful parenting as shown in Figure 1, they are less likely to overreact and discipline their child due to their own strong negative emotions (Duncan et al., 2009). Although the available research in regard to pandemic times is sparse, there are studies that show parents have had elevated levels of stress since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic (Marchetti et al., 2020; Shorey & Ng et al., 2021). It is important to identify

those factors that predict better coping with the challenges of pandemic parenting. Mindful parenting may enable improved parental well-being, and as a result improve overall parent and child relational outcomes (Duncan et al., 2009).

The present study evaluates whether incorporating mindfulness practices into parenting helped parents better navigate the circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic and cope with the changes more effectively. Through the Parenting in the Pandemic Study, 217 participants completed the Interpersonal Mindfulness in Parenting Scale (Duncan, 2009) and the Coping with Pandemic Parenting author-developed question. In analyzing the association between parents' mindful parenting practices and their perceived coping during the pandemic, it is expected that a positive correlation exists between the two variables, thus demonstrating the benefit of mindful parenting in regard to parental well-being.

Demographic Characteristics for Parents and Children Participating in the Parenting in the Pandemic Study (N = 217)

Individual-level variables	n	%
Mothers	98	90.7
Fathers	8	7.4
Other Caregivers	2	1.9
<i>Co-Parenting Relationship</i>		
Yes	166	76.5
No	51	23.5
<i>Parent Employment</i>		
Employment Status Change	57	26.3
Work at home	52	24.1
Work outside the home	65	30.1
Work hybrid	39	18.0
Not employed	60	27.8
<i>Child Gender</i>		
Girl	48	45.3
Boy	57	53.8
Other	1	0.9
<i>Age of Oldest Child</i>		
4, 5, or 6	50	23.6
7, 8, or 9	70	33.0
10, 11, or 12	92	43.4

Table 1: Note: The total study sample N = 217. However, not all participants completed all of the demographic questions, so percentages were calculated based upon the received answers.

METHODS

Participants

The Parenting in the Pandemic Study was open to any parent in the United States with at least one child aged 4 to 12 years. This age range was selected as parents of children of this age were more likely to be responsible for a large amount of home care for their children. The parents of children in this age range were also likely to be significantly impacted by the shutdown of schools in the COVID-19 pandemic (Garbe et al., 2020). The sample consisted of 217 caregivers, whose racial and economic demographics are consistent with the communities from which the participants were taken (Alesina & La Ferrara, 2000). The participants were largely located in the Midwest region of the United States, including Indiana, Iowa, Illinois, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, and Ohio (75.3%, n = 146). Approximately 23.2% of participants were located in the western United States, including Arizona, California, and Colorado (n = 58). Information was collected on parent gender, co-parenting

relationship, employment status, race, location, and the eldest child's gender and age, in addition to the study measures. Descriptive statistics were determined for relevant study sociodemographic variables (Table 1). Note that all socio-demographic questions in the survey were optional, and thus some answers for characteristics in the table are missing.

Parents were recruited to participate in the study through elementary and middle school listserv emails and Facebook social media posts in the Colorado State University and University of Notre Dame communities. The survey was advertised to take approximately 15 to 20 minutes, and participants were compensated with a \$5 gift certificate. One parent per household was permitted to complete the survey. Participant validity was checked using steps similar to Bauermeister and colleagues (2012). Verification procedures for this study included eligibility screening questions, limiting submissions to one per Internet Protocol (IP) address, and cross-checking cases for personal indicators. An estimated survey completion time was calculated, and survey responses that were completed in a nonviable length of time were removed. Surveys with illogical qualitative answers or with less than 25% of the questions answered were also removed. Duplicate and falsified entries were removed by inspecting participants' email addresses, IP address, browser information, and operating systems for overlapping data entries.

Procedure

The survey was administered through Qualtrics (Qualtrics, 2021, Provo) via email from February through May 2021. Each participant was instructed to complete the online survey one time from a location of their choosing. The survey asked the age of the participant's oldest child under 12 years old. Participants were instructed to respond to the survey with that oldest child in consideration. Questions on the survey came from four measures: the Emotion Regulation Checklist (Shields & Cicchetti, 1997), the Interpersonal Mindfulness in Parenting Scale (Duncan, 2009), the Perceived Stress Scale (Cohen et al., 1983), and the Coping with Pandemic Parenting author-developed question. Analyses for this thesis utilized only the measurements from the Interpersonal Mindfulness in Parenting Scale (Duncan, 2009) and the Coping with Pandemic Parenting author-developed question.

All participants were provided information about the study and its purpose and gave informed consent. The protocol of the study was accepted by the Institutional Review Board at Colorado State University (Protocol #3060). Regression analyses were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS, version 22.0, IBM SPSS) to measure associations between interpersonal mindfulness and parent adjustment to the pandemic.

Measurements

Interpersonal Mindfulness in Parenting Scale (IEM-P) (Duncan, 2009): Participants completed IEM-P, a ten-item self-report questionnaire, that is used to measure the dimensions of mindful parenting. Mindful parenting is defined as

intentionally, presently, and non-judgmentally paying attention to your child (Kabat-Zinn, 2003). The questionnaire presented statements regarding everyday experiences, and each item was rated by a parent on its applicability to them on a 5-point scale: 1 = never true; 2 = rarely true; 3 = sometimes true; 4 = often true; and 5 = always true. Items encompass the parent-child relationships in the realm of affective, cognitive, and attitudinal aspects, as well as parental interpersonal mindfulness. The Cronbach's alpha measure of internal consistency for this scale is $\alpha = 0.71$, which is ruled an acceptable level of reliability (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Coping with Pandemic Parenting: Participants responded to an author-developed question, "How well have you been able to adjust to the pandemic?" This item was rated by a parent on a 5-point scale: 1 = not well at all; 2 = slightly well; 3 = moderately well; 4 = very well; and 5 = extremely well.

Table 2

Summary Statistics for the Parenting in the Pandemic Study

Variable	M	SD	r	n
Overall Group			-0.34	
Coping with Pandemic Parenting	2.50	0.92		214
Interpersonal Mindful Parenting Scale	36.00	3.95		196

Note: M and SD represent mean and standard deviation, respectively; r indicates the correlation coefficient, and n indicates the number of participants who completed the study measurement.

Figure 2: Correlation between Parental Mindfulness, via the overall mindful parenting score, and Parent Adjustment to the Pandemic ($n = 196$, $r = -0.34$). The Parenting in the Pandemic survey was administered through Qualtrics, of which participants were instructed to respond with their oldest child under 12 years old in consideration. Measurements included the Interpersonal Mindfulness in Parenting Scale (Duncan, 2009) and the Coping with Pandemic Parenting (author-developed question), "How well have you been able to adjust to the pandemic?" Both items were rated on their applicability on a 5-point scale. Correlation analyses were conducted using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS, version 22.0, IBM SPSS) to measure associations between interpersonal mindfulness and parent adjustment to the pandemic. Note: Due to overplotting, data points have been made partially transparent, so that points that lie on top of other points can be identified by their darker shade.

RESULTS

We found a significant correlation between parental practice of interpersonal mindfulness when parenting and parental adjustment to the stress of the pandemic. There was a negative, linear association between overall parental mindfulness scores and parent adjustment to the pandemic scores (Figure 2). The Pearson correlation coefficient between the two factors was -0.34 , and the two-tailed correlation was significant at the 0.001 level ($n = 196$). Measurement means, standard deviations, and correlations were examined between all study

variables (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

The current study investigated the association between parents' mindful parenting practices and their perceived coping during the pandemic. There is not much available research on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on parental mindfulness and well-being. The Parenting in the Pandemic Study aimed to fill this gap in the relevant literature and explore the importance of mindful parenting and its implications on parental well-being during pandemic times. Research from prior to the pandemic (Bögels et al. 2010; Potharst et al. 2017; Beer et al. 2013) aligns with our findings that more mindful parenting is related to better coping with the pandemic. These findings present significant insights into how the pandemic may have impacted family structure and relationship dynamics; the researchers propose that mindful parenting practices may be a key component to better adjustment and mitigating the effects of elevated stress. The negative, linear association between the Coping with Pandemic Parenting measure and the Interparental Mindful Parenting Scale measure demonstrates a significant positive relationship between the two variables. The interpretation of this relationship may be confusing due to the scaling of the items in the regression analysis. The Interparental Mindful Parenting Scale measure was rated on a five-point scale, with higher scores indicating more mindful parenting. The Coping with Pandemic Parenting measure was also rated on a five-point scale, but in the opposite direction; higher scores on this measure indicated less coping. Thus, the interpretation of this negative correlation shows that more mindful parenting is related to better coping with the pandemic.

This relationship shows the benefits of mindful parenting practices on parental well-being, and as a result improve overall parent and child relational outcomes. These results also align with research conducted prior to the pandemic, which also showed that people who practice mindfulness regularly are better able to cope with elevated levels of stress (Bögels et al. 2010; Potharst et al. 2017; Beer et al. 2013). The restrictions of this pandemic had implications on the social, economic, and mental wellness of families (Goldberg et al. 2020). Thus, mindful parenting practices seemed to serve as a buffer against some of the negative impacts of stress on well-being (Baer et al. 2012).

This major public health crisis has brought significant stress for working parents worldwide (Coyne et al. 2020). Even prior to the pandemic, ensuring the safety and engagement of children in the household can be a challenging duty for many parents, especially for parents with jobs (Cluver et al. 2020). 26.3% of this study's population experienced an employment status change as a result of the pandemic. Single-parent households have also experienced elevated stress due to pandemic implications. Co-parenting families have the benefit of sharing parental duties, as well as the opportunity to support their partner with a break. Single parents are less likely to have these benefits. In addition, the pandemic restrictions prohibited access to social support for these struggling parents. With the

elevated stressors brought about by the pandemic, single parents were at a greater risk for stress and burnout (Swit 2022). Research has also shown that the economic circumstances of single-parent families tend to be inferior to those with multiple caregivers (Guetto et al. 2021). The pandemic has amplified already existing inequalities suffered by single-parent households, such as a growing poverty gap, income stagnation, and declining work-life balance (Nieuwenhuis 2020).

In both measures, the mean scores were quite close to the median point values of both measures. The Coping with Pandemic Parenting score mean lies within the range of 3 ("moderately well") and 4 ("very well") answers. The Interparental Mindful Parenting Scale scores lie within the range of 2 ("rarely true") and 3 ("sometimes true") answers. This lack of extremity could be due to the data relying solely on self-report collection, which may have allowed for social desirability bias to influence parental responses. Parents may have incorrectly estimated their ability to cope with the stressors of the pandemic and were perhaps reluctant to reveal their true feelings for fear of judgment as an inept caretaker.

While the significant findings of this study contribute to the growing literature on mindful parenting, it is important to note some limitations. Internet surveys have many benefits, including low cost, high efficiency, and greater access to larger populations (Arentze et al. 2005). However, they lack some of the qualitative measurements that can be gathered from face-to-face interviews and may be more subject to sampling bias (Hughes 2012). The Coping with Pandemic Parenting measure was evaluated solely using a single author-developed question. Although this was selected in order to limit the length and burden of the Parenting in the Pandemic survey, future studies of this nature should include a more robust measure of parental coping. In addition, the study population was primarily white, upper-middle class mothers. Research has shown that the COVID-19 pandemic has affected different demographic groups in independent ways, bringing about parenting challenges that they may not have previously faced (Brown et al. 2020). Study findings may not generalize to underrepresented populations, and recruitment should expand to more representative populations in the future.

Despite the mentioned limitations, the present study's findings imply that mindful parenting is associated with elevated parental coping abilities in the circumstances of COVID-19. The effects of the pandemic on families are likely to linger far beyond the lockdown, and the significance of its psychological implications on family dynamics is yet to be determined (Giusti et al. 2020). Although this study measures mindful parenting within the context of COVID-19, its effects will stretch into future research. Mindful parenting does not only help with parental coping, but also may enable improved parental well-being, and as a result improve overall parent and child relational outcomes (Duncan et al. 2009). These preliminary outcomes bring attention to the importance of continued research in the realm of mindful parenting, and perhaps illuminate a coping method for stressed parents and their children.

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Participation of SOCS Proteins in Multiple Sclerosis and Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis

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ABSTRACT

The suppressors of cytokine signaling (SOCS) proteins act on the Janus kinase/signal transducer and activator of transcription (JAK/STAT) signaling pathway to modulate the inflammatory response. It is believed that the expression of these proteins is altered in the pathophysiology of multiple sclerosis, though no comprehensive study has aimed to address this knowledge gap. Here, we review recent findings on the participation of the SOCS proteins in multiple sclerosis and its most common animal model, experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis, to elucidate their pathophysiological relationships more fully. We executed an exhaustive literature search on PubMed and SciELO with the words “multiple sclerosis” or “experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis” and each SOCS member. The analysis of these findings indicates the potential clinical advantages to the study of the SOCS proteins and provides a framework for further investigation into this pathophysiological relationship.

Keywords: multiple sclerosis, experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis, SOCS proteins

INTRODUCTION

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic and degenerative autoimmune disease of the central nervous system, characterized by inflammation and demyelination in both the brain and spinal cord [1,2]. Four forms of MS have been reported: the relapsing-remitting form (RRMS), the secondary progressive form (SPMS), the primary progressive form (PPMS), and the progressive-relapsing form (PRMS) [1]. RRMS is the most common form that patients present, accounting for greater than 80% of cases, although 60% of RRMS patients will transition to the secondary progressive form within 10–15 years [3]. Approximately 15% of patients present the PPMS form at the disease onset, and very few individuals present the progressive-relapsing form [1]. One of the most characterized mouse models of MS, experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE), is commonly used to study the disease in vivo due to its clinical and histopathological similarities to MS [2]. The foremost instrument used to assess the clinical severity of the disease is the Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS). The EDSS is a clinically administered evaluation of central nervous system function, graded from zero to ten in half-point intervals. A score of zero indicates normal neurological status,

while a score of ten indicates death due to MS [3].

Worldwide, it is estimated that 2.8 million individuals have MS, with females more predisposed to develop the disease than males by a ratio of 2:1. Since 2013, both prevalence and incidence have increased; it is now estimated that someone is diagnosed with MS every five minutes [4]. Risk factors are believed to be both genetic and environmental, including human leukocyte antigen (HLA) complex variants, Epstein-Barr virus infection, smoking, low vitamin D levels due to lack of sun exposure, and childhood obesity [5]. Treatment of MS is primarily based in disease-modifying therapies with the interferons or glatiramer acetate (GA), which work by suppressing or modulating immune function [6].

The etiology of MS remains unclear, along with the molecular mechanisms that underlie the disease progression. However, the participation of various proinflammatory cytokines acting on the JAK/STAT pathway has been reported [1]. These cytokines include, but are not limited to, interleukin 6 (IL-6), IL-17, IL-23, and interferon- γ (IFN- γ). Critical to the regulation of this pathway is the family of the suppressors of cytokine signaling (SOCS) proteins, composed of eight members: SOCS1–7 and CIS [1]. The relationship between these SOCS proteins and MS or EAE remains unclear. In this review, the findings of various studies focused on the SOCS proteins and either MS or EAE are compiled to more fully elucidate the participation of SOCS proteins in these pathophysiologicals.

METHODS

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram for the article identification process. Using the aforementioned selection criteria, 88 articles were found prior to screening. After the screening process, 12 articles were chosen to be included in this review.

An exhaustive literature search on PubMed and SciELO was carried out with the words “multiple sclerosis” or “experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis” and each member of the SOCS family. Articles were filtered to only include original research results published from 2012 to 2022 in English or Spanish. After these criteria were applied, remaining articles were screened according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) formula (Fig. 1) [7].

RESULTS

Twelve articles which satisfied the selection criteria and the screening process for this literature review were found. Seven of these articles analyze the relationship between SOCS proteins and MS, and five analyze the relationship between SOCS proteins and EAE. Furthermore, SOCS1 is studied in six of the articles, SOCS2 in two, SOCS3 in eight, SOCS5 in two, and SOCS7 in one of the articles. SOCS4, SOCS6, and CIS were not the object of study in any of the articles that satisfied the selection process.

3.1 SOCS proteins and MS

With respect to the seven articles that analyzed the relationship between SOCS proteins and MS, Sedeño-Monge et al. 2014 is the oldest included in this review. The authors of this study analyzed via RT-qPCR the blood samples of 38 RRMS patients and 2 SPMS patients being treated with either IFN- β or GA. They found transcription levels of SOCS1 to be significantly reduced in patients with MS when compared to healthy controls; SOCS3 transcription levels were significantly enhanced in these patients [8]. Supporting this evidence, when the RNA from blood samples of a larger group of 50 RRMS patients was analyzed by RT-qPCR, SOCS1 and SOCS5 transcription levels were found to be significantly reduced in comparison to healthy individuals [9]. However, comparison of SOCS2 and SOCS3 expression showed no significant differences between RRMS patients and healthy individuals [9]. Additional studies showed no significant differences in SOCS1 and SOCS3 transcription levels. In one such study that analyzed the blood samples of 33 female RRMS patients via RT-qPCR, there was no significant difference in SOCS1 expression between the RRMS patients and selected controls [10]. Similarly, a later study analyzed via enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) the protein in blood samples from 36 RRMS patients (18 of whom had been treated with exercise for eight weeks while the other 18 were treated with relaxation). The results demonstrated the baseline levels of SOCS1 and SOCS3 were similar between the 36 RRMS patients and 18 control subjects [11]. Additionally, Ozkul and colleagues (2018) found that SOCS1 and SOCS3 levels did not change significantly after eight weeks in the exercise group; however, SOCS1 did show a significant increase after the eight-week period in the relaxation group [11].

In contrast to these data, when the blood samples of 30 men and women with RRMS being treated with IFN- β were analyzed by RT-qPCR, SOCS1 expression was found to be enhanced in patients with RRMS compared to 30 age- and gen-

der-matched healthy individuals [12]. In a more recent study, protein samples were analyzed via ELISA from 31 female and 14 male RRMS patients being treated with IFN- β -1. Pietrzak and colleagues (2020) found a positive correlation between baseline EDSS scores and SOCS3 expression and, surprisingly, after 24 months of treatment, SOCS3 levels were lower in patients with better clinical prognoses [13].

In regards to SOCS5 and SOCS7 expression changes, there appeared to be significant differences in SOCS7 in RRMS patients treated with GA, according to Rojas-Morales and colleagues (2019) [1]. The RT-qPCR analysis from the blood samples of 36 RRMS patients showed that the baseline levels of SOCS5 and SOCS7 were similar between the 36 RRMS patients and controls [1]. Treatment with varying levels of IFN- β for 25 of the RRMS patients and treatment of the same level of GA for the other 11 patients showed that neither treatment altered the levels of SOCS5 and that there is an insignificant correlation between SOCS5 and EDSS [1]. However, treatment with GA increased the levels of SOCS7 and showed a significant correlation between SOCS7 and EDSS score, where higher amounts of transcript resulted in higher disability [1]. In 33 of the 36 RRMS patients, IFN- γ , IL-6, and IL-17 levels were also measured and only IFN- γ concentrations varied significantly with IFN- β or GA treatment [1].

3.2 SOCS proteins and EAE

We identified five articles that analyzed the relationship between SOCS proteins and EAE. In the first of these studies, Qin and colleagues (2012) induced EAE in mice of a SOCS3fl/fl group or LysMCre-SOCS3fl/fl group via the peptide MOG35-55 and conducted analyses via RT-qPCR and ELISA. They found that the suppression of SOCS3 in LysMCre-SOCS3fl/fl mice resulted in an atypical form of EAE, different from the classical form exhibited by the SOCS3fl/fl mice, possibly due to the increased activation of STAT3 and STAT4 [14]. Furthermore, the suppression of SOCS3 correlated with an elevated expression of cytokines [14]. In a separate study, when 48 female mice were divided into a control group and an EAE group, the mice in the EAE group had the disease induced via the peptide MOG35-55 and analysis was conducted via RT-qPCR. Over the course of 30 days, SOCS3 transcription increased through days 7 and 14, but fell by day 21; expression of the cytokines IFN- γ and IL-17, analyzed via ELISA, peaked on day 21 of the 30-day period [15]. In another SOCS3 study, when Yan and colleagues (2019) analyzed blood samples from mice divided into a SOCS3fl/fl group and a SOCS3 Δ LysM group using RT-qPCR, they found that mice with a SOCS3 deficiency showed greater demyelination in the cerebellum at the peak of EAE when compared to the control mice [2]. Loss of SOCS3 resulted in the continuous activation of STAT3, suggesting that SOCS3 plays a role in the negative regulation of STAT3 signaling [2].

In a SOCS2 study, when EAE-induced mice were analyzed by western blot in a control group or a SOCS2-/- group, SOCS2-deficient mice showed better motor function and

control with weight-loss when compared to the SOCS2 control mice [16]. Loss of SOCS2 resulted in a strong resistance to the development of EAE, suggesting that SOCS2 plays a role in the modulation of inflammation [16]. However, the SOCS2-deficient mice were unable to recover from EAE in the same capacity as the control mice [16]. In a separate study, 50 female EAE-induced mice were divided into five groups: one control group, one group with EAE induced via the peptide MOG35-55, and three groups with EAE induced via the peptide MOG35-55 and treated with varying doses of Rapamycin. When mice were analyzed 21 days after EAE induction, RT-qPCR and western blot analysis showed SOCS1 and SOCS3 expression were significantly enhanced in the Rapamycin groups in comparison to the controls group; SOCS3 expression was significantly reduced in the EAE group in comparison to controls [17]. Furthermore, the protein expression of IFN- γ and IL-17 analyzed via ELISA were significantly enhanced in the EAE group in comparison to both the control group and Rapamycin groups [17].

DISCUSSION

During our literature screening, it was evident that there was a large gap in the body of research for each member of the SOCS family. That is, SOCS1 and SOCS3 have been investigated markedly more than any of the other SOCS members. In contrast, SOCS4, SOCS6, and CIS are included in very few studies, none of which satisfied the selection criteria of this review. We suggest the scientific community may benefit from investigation of these less-explored proteins. Further, nearly every MS patient that participated in the studies included in this review were relapsing-remitting (RRMS) patients. Although more difficult due to prevalence factors, the scientific community may also benefit from more intentionality in including SPMS, PPMS, and PRMS patients in these studies.

We discovered much contradictory data within the results of the seven articles included in this review that analyze the SOCS proteins and MS. For example, two studies found that the transcription levels of SOCS1 in MS patients were significantly reduced compared to those in healthy controls [8,9]. In contrast, two other studies found no significant difference in SOCS1 transcription levels between MS patients and control groups [10,11], and a third study found SOCS1 to be significantly enhanced in MS patients compared to healthy controls [12]. These discrepancies are not limited to SOCS1 results. Sedeño-Monge and colleagues (2014) showed SOCS3 expression to be significantly enhanced in MS patients compared to healthy controls [8]. However, two other studies did not find notable differences in SOCS3 expression between the two groups [9,11]. Further, while Toghi and colleagues (2017) showed SOCS5 expression to be significantly reduced in MS patients compared to controls [9], Rojas-Morales and colleagues (2019) did not find a significant difference between the two groups [1]. One plausible explanation for these contradictory results could stem from the investigation methods used by each study. Although the majority of studies utilized RT-qPCR, Ozkul and colleagues (2018) and Pietrzak and colleagues (2020) utilized

ELISA to analyze proteins. Curiously, differences were still observed in studies that used identical investigation methods. Therefore, future studies may need to include multiple methods for RNA and protein analysis to further contextualize these results.

Lastly, in addition to using mice as subjects instead of human patients, the five articles in this review that analyzed the SOCS proteins and EAE had a greater focus on analyzing cytokines than the MS studies. Cytokines that were most frequently analyzed in these articles are IL-6, IL-17, IL-23, and IFN- γ . This correlated with the SOCS proteins that were most frequently studied in these articles since, as Morris and colleagues (2018) argued in their review of JAK/STAT cytokine signaling, SOCS1 plays a role in regulating several cytokines (IL-2,-4,-7,-9,-12,-13,-15,-21,-23, IFN γ / α/β , and TSLP) and SOCS3 plays a role in regulating IL-6,-11,-27,-31, LIF, OSM, CNTF, CT-1, CLC, G-CSF, and LEP [18]. However, coinciding with the absence of studies of SOCS proteins that are not SOCS1 or SOCS3, there was an absence of studies of cytokines that are not controlled by SOCS1 or SOCS3.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, numerous studies investigating the relationship between SOCS1 and SOCS3 and MS and EAE have been realized. However, further investigation is necessary to better understand contradictory results regarding SOCS1, SOCS3, and SOCS5 and to more fully explore SOCS2, SOCS4, SOCS6, SOCS7, and CIS along with their associated cytokines and non-RRMS forms of the disease. A better understanding of these pathophysiologies could play an important role in the future of preclinical prognoses and clinical treatment strategies.

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Sleep Duration Variability Moderates the Effect of Cortisol Reactivity on Negative Affect in Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

The way in which adolescents react to acute stressors significantly predicts their emotional health. Stress reactivity can be measured through cortisol, a hormone secreted when the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis is stimulated. Although excess stress reactivity is associated with socioemotional problems, evidence indicates healthy sleep may moderate this relationship. However, little is known about the effect of sleep patterns on cortisol and negative affect in rural adolescents. Therefore, this study uses a sample of rural adolescents to investigate 1) if cortisol reactivity levels predict negative affect and 2) how sleep duration buffers this risk link. Data were collected over 18 months from 126 adolescents in rural Georgia (mean age = 12.9). Actigraphy watches were used to assess sleep duration variability (i.e., irregularity in daily hours slept per week). Cortisol reactivity levels were obtained 20 minutes after the Trier Social Stress Test from saliva samples, and the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule was used to assess negative affect at T1 and T2 ($\alpha = .88$). A structural equation modeling framework was used to test all hypotheses. Preliminary analyses showed no direct effect of cortisol reactivity on negative affect ($\beta = -.012, p > .05$); however, a significant interaction effect between cortisol reactivity and sleep duration variability on negative affect was observed ($\beta = -.931, p < .05$). Johnson-Neyman and simple slopes showed high sleep variability intensifies negative affect in adolescents with low cortisol reactivity but reduces negative affect for adolescents with high cortisol reactivity. This preliminary research informs healthy sleep guidelines for adolescents and warrants future studies to be tested in other populations.

INTRODUCTION

Excessive stress is known to cause a variety of psychological and socioemotional problems (Doane & Zeiders, 2014; Duprey et al., 2021). The stress response begins when the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis is stimulated, releasing a cascade of hormones between the hypothalamus, anterior pituitary gland, and adrenal gland (Fig. 1). While many hormones are for chemical signaling in this pathway, the final output of this system is cortisol, a hormone which travels throughout the body and induces a variety of metabolic effects. Therefore, cortisol is a valid and reliable measure of the stress response (Dedovic et al., 2009) One method of measuring cortisol is

through cortisol reactivity, which measures immediate fluctuations in cortisol in response to a stressor. Improper functioning of the HPA axis can result in hyperactivity and increased cortisol reactivity (Hankin et al., 2010).

While many external factors can stimulate the HPA axis, it's well established that inadequate sleep intensifies the relationship between cortisol and negative functional outcomes pertaining to somatic and psychosocial health (Mrug et al., 2016; Shochat et al., 2014). In particular, poor sleep quality has been shown to potentiate the stress reactivity of the HPA axis (van Dalen & Markus, 2018), and this finding has been shown in older adults when poor sleep co-occurs with other emotional and behavioral problems (Pesonen et al., 2014). On the other hand, healthy sleep duration has been found to reduce cortisol secretion, protecting older adults from negative outcomes (Rueggeberg et al., 2012). Thus, sleep has the potential to be both a protective mechanism and a risk factor in the stress pathway.

Although adolescence is a critical developmental period, less is known about the relationship between sleep, cortisol, and subsequent negative affect in adolescents within a rural population. Rural adolescents may face unique stressors, including cost of healthcare, stigma for depression, lack of information regarding medical resources, and poor insurance coverage, which put them at a greater risk for maladaptive outcomes (Elliott & Larson, 2004). Additionally, due to the increased number of notable stressful life events during adolescence, such as puberty, graduation, and transition to college, it is critical to understand the biological and environmental mechanisms underlying psychological outcomes (Doane & Zeiders, 2014). Therefore, there is a need to understand risk and resilience factors that affect development during adolescents in rural areas.

Figure 1. The HPA axis communicates using cortisol, among other hormones. Reprinted from "Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal Axis," by BioRender.com (2022). Retrieved from <https://app.biorender.com/biorender-templates>

The present study used a rural adolescent population to investigate the role of sleep regarding cortisol and negative affect. Here, we utilized a longitudinal study to investigate the moderating role of sleep duration variability on the relationship

between cortisol reactivity and negative affect. We hypothesized that (1) there would be a main effect of cortisol reactivity on negative affect, and (2) sleep duration variability would moderate this relationship.

METHODS

The study used a longitudinal design consisting of two waves over 18 months. 126 adolescents were recruited from the rural community surrounding Athens, Georgia (mean age = 12.9). The first wave of data collection took place from January 2018 to March 2020, and the second wave of data collection took place from May 2020 to October 2020. The racial-ethnic composition of the sample was 78.8% European American, 11.5% African American, 3.8% Latinx, 1.0% Asian/Pacific Islander, and 4.8% Other. All participants completed the study voluntarily and were assigned a random ID number to protect their anonymity. Participant names and ID numbers were stored in an encrypted database only accessible by lab members. To assess sleep duration variability (i.e., irregularity in daily hours slept per week), participants wore actigraphy watches over the course of seven days. The Trier Social Stress Test was administered and cortisol reactivity levels were obtained via saliva samples 20 minutes after. The Positive Affect and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS) was used to assess negative affect at T1 and T2 ($\alpha = .88$). A structural equation modeling framework was used to test the main effect of cortisol reactivity on negative affect, as well as the moderating role of sleep duration variability (Fig. 2).

RESULTS

Regarding aim 1, our preliminary analyses yielded no main effect of cortisol reactivity on negative affect ($\beta = -.012, p > .05$). Regarding aim 2, however, a significant interaction effect was found between cortisol reactivity and sleep duration variability on negative affect ($\beta = -.931, p < .05$). Further analyses using Johnson-Neyman and simple slopes showed the critical role of high sleep variability. In adolescents with low cortisol reactivity, high sleep variability intensified negative affect, but reduced negative affect for adolescents with high cortisol reactivity (Fig. 3). Upon probing, the low sleep variability group was found to be less applicable to participants than the high sleep variability group (Fig. 4).

DISCUSSION

The above results demonstrate that the effect of sleep variability on negative affect is dependent upon an individual's cortisol reactivity. Therefore, cortisol reactivity is a key factor when predicting emotional outcomes for rural adolescents. When considering individual differences in environmental sensitivity, this critical difference in cortisol reactivity can be understood. Certain individuals are theorized to be extremely sensitive to environmental factors, such as sleep and cortisol, while others may not have as intense of a reaction (Pluess, 2015; Schriber & Guyer, 2016). These biological predispositions therefore make some individuals very sensitive to their environment, while others are quite resistant to environmental stressors.

Figure 2. Sleep duration variability moderates the link between cortisol reactivity and negative affect.

Figure 3. High sleep variability intensifies negative affect with high cortisol reactivity, while the reverse is true for low cortisol.

Figure 4. After probing, the high sleep variability line in Figure 3 is applicable to 56.9% of participants, while the low sleep variability line is only applicable to 4.2% of participants.

However, future studies are needed to replicate these findings in other populations. Limitations of this study include only two time points used in the longitudinal analysis and no objective measure of negative affect in adolescents. Additionally, participants were only recruited from rural communities in Georgia. In order to sufficiently generalize these results, a broader sample is needed across the United States and internationally. By replicating this study in other samples, these findings will be more robust.

Continued on next page.

Understanding how individuals react differently to their environment is key to understanding human development. This study demonstrates how healthy sleep (and unhealthy sleep) affect the HPA axis and psychological outcomes during adolescence, a time of heightened stress for many (Dedovic et al., 2009; Mrug et al., 2016). On a broader scale, this preliminary research informs healthy sleep guidelines for adolescents and highlights the importance of later educational start times, in order to encourage adequate sleep during adolescence. Future directions could investigate the impact of cortisol and sleep duration on other psychological constructs, including aggression, externalizing symptoms, and depression.

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An Accessible Quantitative Exploration of Gravitational Lensing

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ABSTRACT

Einstein's general theory of relativity predicts the phenomenon of gravitational lensing: the process by which the gravitational field of a massive object bends the path of light. This effect is apparent when a bright light source is positioned behind the lensing object, and the image of the light source is distorted from the position of the Earth. This paper presents an accessible method to determine the mass of a space object that exhibits gravitational lensing, such that any citizen scientists or students interested in astronomy can conduct research regarding this phenomenon. Seven objects exhibiting gravitational lensing were selected for analysis, four of which had literature mass values. The masses of these objects were calculated using the angles of the refracted light and the distances from the objects to Earth. All images were collected and processed using free, publicly available sky surveys, demonstrating the minimal barriers to the method's use. The percent error on the calculations for the known mass objects varied widely for each object, ranging from 4.48% to $5.77 \times 105\%$. The magnitude of these error calculations likely stems from the simplifying assumptions made to develop this method in a manner that is accessible for use without a firm understanding of advanced astrophysical concepts. Though the initial formulation of this method seems to achieve its designated purpose of enabling anyone with internet access to calculate the mass of space objects exhibiting gravitational lensing, further research is required to determine the accuracy of this method—including establishing which factors have the most influence over the accuracy of mass calculations—and develop a firm understanding of its limitations.

INTRODUCTION

Gravitational lensing is defined as the process by which the path of light from a source (the background/lensed object) is refracted by the gravitational field of an interposing, massive object (the foreground/lensing object), resulting in a different apparent position of the lensed object from a distant observer's point of view. This occurs because light follows null geodesics, the natural path of spacetime, and thus has its path bent by gravitational fields.

The derivations of the equations required for this method are based on multiple simplifying assumptions. First, it is assumed that the gravitational potential energy of the light passing over the lensing object divided by the speed of light squared is far less than one. This assumption is required to apply the Born approximation, which is only applicable if the scattered field is relatively small. Second, the lensing object is approximated to

be a point mass in order to create a more generally applicable equation. Third, it is assumed that the observer, lensing object, and lensed object are all in alignment to simplify angle calculations. Finally, it is assumed that angle θ_{new} is far less than 2π to apply trigonometric small angle approximations.

With these assumptions stated, the derivation begins with a statement of Snell's Law, defining the index of refraction as the refraction of the lensing object's gravitational field. The line element of weak gravity is set equal to zero, meaning that light will precisely follow the path laid out for it by a weak gravitational field, to solve for said index of refraction. From there, a series of path integrals between arbitrary points λ_a and λ_b and using ∇_{\perp} as the gradient perpendicular to the light path yields the equation for θ_{new} (the angle by which the light is bent):

$$\overrightarrow{\theta}_{new} = \frac{2}{c^2} \int_{\lambda_b}^{\lambda_a} \overrightarrow{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi d\lambda \quad (1)$$

This derivation is abbreviated for the sake of concision. A full derivation up until this point can be found in Professor Zaidouni's lecture notes (Ref. 1).

From there, the Born approximation (Ref. 2) can be applied with the impact parameter b (defined as the distance between the path of a projectile and the center of a potential field which, in this case, is the position of the point mass) and the distance of approach u (with $u=0$ defined as the closest distance). This gives a numerically solvable integral bounded between infinity and negative infinity instead of two arbitrary points on the path, resulting in the equation

$$\overrightarrow{\theta}_{new} = \frac{2}{c^2} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \overrightarrow{\nabla}_{\perp} \Phi db \quad (2)$$

To apply this to a point mass, the impact parameter b must be determined in terms of x and y , giving

$$b = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \quad (3)$$

Using the gravitational potential energy of light

$$\Phi = \frac{-GM}{r} \quad (4)$$

and the redefined impact parameter, the angle θ_{new} can be defined by its x and y components, yielding

$$\overrightarrow{\theta}_{new,x}(b) = \frac{4GM}{c^2 b} \sin(\Phi) \quad (5)$$

$$\overrightarrow{\theta}_{new,y}(b) = \frac{4GM}{c^2 b} \cos(\Phi) \quad (6)$$

Which, when recombined, simplifies to

$$|\vec{\theta}_{new}| = \frac{4GM}{c^2b} \quad (5)$$

And can also be written as

$$\frac{|\vec{\theta}_{new}|c^2b}{4G} = M \quad (7)$$

Using the assumption of object alignment and small angle approximations, the impact parameter b can be rewritten as an arc length using θ_{new} and d (the distance to the object), giving the final equation of

$$M = \frac{|\vec{\theta}_{new}|^2c^2d}{4G} \quad (8)$$

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The following method requires only openly accessible databases to take measurements. This low barrier for use makes our method ideal for citizen scientists, astronomy students, and enthusiasts. A lensing object is selected from *SkyView*, and the distance of the lensing object to the passing light of the lensed image is measured using the pixels of the image and database coordinates. These data are then used in combination with publicly available distance values to solve for the mass of the lensing object.

Object Selection

To test this simplified method, we selected a range of representative objects, four with masses available from the literature, and three of unknown masses. Candidates for this experiment were selected from a variety of gravitational lensing databases and academic journals, filtered to find those with known distances from Earth. Candidates with multiple instances of lensing or nearly circular lensing were prioritized for closer alignment of the Earth, lensing object, and lensed object. The stellar coordinates and distance from Earth for each object were recorded.

Digital Surveys and Images

Next, the stellar coordinates of the object were input into *SkyView*, a public database of sky surveys. All available surveys on the query form were selected, with the initial image parameters set to the default values that *SkyView* provides (300 pixels with varying degree size based on the survey). The surveys were then requested and viewed.

Survey results displaying only a black screen were removed from the list of requested surveys. Results that displayed an image were then analyzed to determine if they sufficiently displayed the expected image of gravitational lensing by comparing the survey results to images from the academic journals or databases from which the objects were selected. If the survey did not demonstrate the expected image of gravitational lens-

ing but instead exhibited something similar, the image size in pixels and degrees were rescaled to better display the instance of lensing.

Once the requested images fully displayed the gravitational lensing process as seen in the comparison photo, the surveys were manually filtered for the images of the highest resolution and clearest manifestation of lensing. Based on these criteria, the best survey was selected for coordinate collection.

Coordinate Collection

By hovering a mouse over the requested image, *SkyView* displays the precise coordinates of the point that the mouse is above, given by right ascension and declination to one one-hundredth and one-tenth an arcsecond respectively. This process can be carried out with precision down to a half-pixel of the image displayed by the survey. Through this process, the precise coordinates of the lensing object were collected by visually determining the center pixel of the object and approximating the object's center (and therefore center of mass by the point-mass approximation) within the centermost pixel. These coordinates were then recorded. Similarly, this process was also carried out on the lensed object by visually determining the center point of the image being bent around the foreground object. If the background object is displayed more than once around the foreground object, this collection process is repeated on the lensed object multiple times. These coordinates were then recorded. Two images from *SkyView* centered on lensing objects are shown below.

Figure 1 - The image of LRG 3-757 from the SkyView SDSSdr7g survey used to collect data.

Figure 2 - The image of GAL-CLUS-022058s from the SkyView DSS: Original Digitized Sky Survey used to collect data.

DATA

Seven objects were analyzed using the process detailed above. All *SkyView* survey results can be found in Appendix B, while the data obtained from the *SkyView* surveys can be found in Appendix A.

For the rest of the collected data, including information about the type of survey used and the image size for each object, see Appendix A.

Object	Distance to Object
LRG3-757	5.2 billion light-years (Ref. 3)
GAL-CLUS-022058s	9.4 billion light-years (Ref. 4)
HST 14176+5226	7 billion light-years (Ref. 5)
ZW2237+030	0.5 billion light years (Ref. 6)
J210415.89-062024.7	$z = 0.216$ (redshift) (Ref. 7) (2.97 billion light years)
HST 15433+5352	$z = 0.497$ (redshift) (Ref. 8) (6.84 billion light years)

Table 1. The literature values for the distances from each object to Earth in the units that the literature provided. Literature values in units of redshift were converted to light-years for the calculations.

ANALYSIS

Calculations

In order to obtain the angle of refraction, the coordinates of the lensing object and the lensed object were collected. The right ascension was then converted into degrees from the original units of arc hours, arcminutes, and arcseconds. The angle between the center of the lensing object and apparent position of the lensed object is sampled at multiple locations and averaged to reduce error.

The processed angular data with fuller treatment in Appendix A are as follows:

Object	Survey Source	Angle (θ) (radians)
LRG3-757	Sloan Digital Sky Survey g-band DR7	2.566487×10^{-5}
GAL-CLUS-022058s	Original Digitized Sky Survey	5.217546×10^{-5}
HST 14176+5226	WISE 3.4 Micron All-Sky Survey	1.217188×10^{-4}
ZW2237+030	UKIRT Infrared Deep Survey J-band	4.354345×10^{-6}
J210415.89-062024.7	First Digitized Sky Survey: Blue Plates	2.389931×10^{-5}
HST 15433+5352	First Digitized Sky Survey: Blue Plates	5.281157×10^{-5}
JVAS B1938+666	WISE 4.6 Micron All-Sky Survey	1.737398×10^{-4}

Table 2. The coordinate data of Appendix A have been converted into radians. All significant figures are preserved for later steps.

Then, the raw values of Table 2 are converted into meters.

Object	Distance to Object (m)
LRG3-757	4.6515×10^{25}
GAL-CLUS-022058s	8.8930×10^{25}
HST 14176+5226	$6.6225113308 \times 10^{25}$
ZW2237+030	$4.730365236 \times 10^{24}$
J210415.89-062024.7	$2.3651826181 \times 10^{25}$
HST 15433+5352	6.475×10^{25}
JVAS B1938+666	2.682×10^{23}

Table 3. The literature values as referenced in Table 1 converted from their initial units into meters. All significant figures are preserved for later steps.

RESULTS

The following masses were calculated using (8) and the data from Tables 2 and 3.

Object	Calculated Mass (kg)	Accepted Mass Value (kg)	Percent Error
LRG3-757	1.09×10^{43}	1.04×10^{43} (Ref. 10)	4.89%
GAL-CLUS-022058s	8.15×10^{43}	6.67×10^{44} ($\pm 9.95 \times 10^{43}$) (Ref. 11)	88.8%
HST 14176+5226*	3.30×10^{44}	Unknown	-
ZW2237+030*	3.02×10^{40}	Unknown	-
J210415.89-062024.7	4.55×10^{42}	3.38×10^{40} ($\pm 1.19 \times 10^{39}$) (Ref. 7)	$1.34 \times 10^{4\%}$
HST 15433+5352*	6.08×10^{43}	Unknown	-
JVAS B1938+666	9.42×10^{44}	1.63×10^{41} (Ref. 12)	$5.77 \times 10^{5\%}$

Table 4. The calculated mass of each object, and the literature values and percent error for objects with an accepted mass value.

All calculated masses were rounded to three significant figures due to the inherent limitations of low-resolution images. Were the resolution not considered, all masses would be rounded to five significant figures.

Three of the seven calculated masses are the first calculated mass of their respective objects. These masses were included in the calculations, as they indicate how this method can be used. For those interested in learning about gravitational lensing and calculating mass values for space objects based on this phenomenon, calculating a potential mass value and mass error bounds for an object without an accepted literature value would be an engaging way to interact with research.

Two of the objects with known masses were relatively accurate with respect to other methods of calculation (see errors of GAL-CLUS-022058s and J210415.89-062024.7). However, two calculated masses demonstrated extreme deviation from their accepted values. The percent error of calculated mass for objects with known values ranges from 4.85% to $5.77 \times 10^{5\%}$, revealing significant variability in the accuracy of our methods.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE STUDIES

While our results provide a first approximation of accuracy of our experimental methods in approximating the mass of objects exhibiting gravitational lensing, there is not nearly enough data to verify this approach. Further experimentation with objects of known mass is required to verify the accuracy of our method and confirm our hypothesis.

In addition, we made several initial assumptions that could lead to inaccurate results. It is possible that the observer,

lensing object, and lensed object are not all in alignment. The largest simplifying assumption that we made was that the lensing object is a point mass. Some of our lensing objects were galaxies, and their mass distribution could affect the passing light in irregular ways. This was an extreme simplification and could greatly influence the accuracy of our results.

Future work could involve selecting a larger pool of candidates to quantify the accuracy of this method more precisely. In addition, calculating the mass of more objects with this method could lead to insights on what factors influence its accuracy, perhaps including the magnitude of already determined mass values and the distance from Earth.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This experiment developed and tested a method for calculating the mass of space objects by using the principles of gravitational lensing. After using free sky surveys to gather position data and finding literature values for the objects' distance to Earth, the mass values of seven different objects were calculated with percent error for objects with known mass values ranging from 4.85% to $5.77 \times 10^5\%$ for objects with known mass values. Based on these preliminary calculations, this method appears to provide a rudimentary estimate of an object's mass without direct access to telescopes or imaging software. However, much more analysis of space objects exhibiting gravitational lensing using this method will be necessary to determine its true accuracy due to the vast variation in error.

While the results produced by this method are significantly less precise than those used to find the accepted mass values of space objects, the purpose of this method was not to reduce error, but to create a tool available to novice astronomers. Anyone with internet access can calculate mass values for space objects by finding examples of gravitational lensing, querying *SkyView* for an image of the lensed light, and finding the measured angle between the observer, the center of the lensing object, and the apparent position of the lensed object. This makes it perfect for students as young as high school to get interested in astronomy and collect their own data. This method provides amateur astronomers the ability to conduct measurements for their own research that may have not been possible otherwise.

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We acknowledge the use of NASA's *SkyView* facility (<http://skyview.gsfc.nasa.gov>) located at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center.

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APPENDIX A:

Name	Survey	Image size (pixels)	Image size (°)	Foreground Object Coordinates		Background Object Coordinates 1		Background Object Coordinates 2		Background Object Coordinates 3		Background Object Coordinates 4	
				RA	DEC	RA	DEC	RA	DEC	RA	DEC	RA	DEC
LRG 3-757	SDSSdr7g	300	0.01	11h 48m 33.15s	19° 30m 3.4s	11h 48m 32.83s	19° 30m 5.8s	11h 48m 33.30s	19° 29m 59.2s	11h 48m 33.38s	19° 30m 8.0s	-	-
GAL-CLUS-0220582	DSS: Original	400	0.03	2h 20m 57.59s	-38° 33m 4.27s	2h 20m 56.82s	-38° 33m 6.8s	2h 20m 58.08s	-38° 33m 10.6s	-	-	-	-
HST 14176+5226	WISE 3.4	400	0.018	14h 17m 35.74s	52° 26m 46.2s	14h 17m 33.95s	52° 26m 42.0s	14h 17m 37.25s	52° 26m 50.4s	-	-	-	-
ZW 2237+030	UKIDSS-J	600	0.0031	22h 40m 30.23s	3° 21m 31.0s	22h 40m 30.23s	3° 21m 30.2s	22h 40m 30.19s	3° 21m 31.7s	22h 40m 30.27s	3° 21m 31.3s	22h 40m 30.17s	3° 21m 30.7s
J210415.89-062024.7	DSS1: Blue	400	0.005	21h 4m 15.86s	-6° 20m 24.3s	21h 4m 15.88s	-6° 20m 29.2s	21h 4m 15.53s	-6° 20m 24.3s	-	-	-	-
HST 15433+5352	DSS1: Blue	400	0.0053	15h 43m 20.80s	53° 51m 51.3s	15h 43m 21.46s	53° 51m 57.2s	15h 43m 21.22s	53° 51m 59.4s	-	-	-	-
JVAS B1938+666	WISE 4.6	400	0.015	19h 38m 25.42s	66° 48m 52.8s	19h 38m 22.76s	66° 49m 3.0s	19h 38m 27.36s	66° 48m 43.7s	-	-	-	-

Table A1. The raw, unprocessed data recorded for each object using various sky surveys and image sizes. As each object is different and lenses a variety of space objects, the number of background object coordinates changes based on which object is being considered. Not all objects have four background object coordinates to consider.

APPENDIX B:

Determinantal Inequalities in Minors of Totally Positive Matrices

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ABSTRACT

The relations between minors of totally positive matrices can be used to study many interesting problems in mathematics, physics, and chemistry. Here, we focus on one such inequality, $S_k^2 \geq S_{k+1} \cdot S_{k-1}$. In this paper, we present the proofs of several specific and sub-cases of the inequality (though the general case remains unproved). Additionally, we prove a general formula for the construction of a cluster of Plücker coordinates.

INTRODUCTION

In this section, we define some preliminaries which will be used throughout the paper. We reference [1] and [2] as motivation for our definitions and lemmas included in the introduction.

Definition 1. Let A be a matrix. A minor of A is the determinant of some smaller square matrix formed by removing an appropriate number of rows and columns from A .

Remark 1.1. A minor of a matrix A will be denoted by some index sets i and j and the symbol Δ , namely, $\Delta_{i,j}$. The elements of this index set denote which rows and columns of A are kept. As an example, if A is a 4×4 matrix, $\Delta_{12,12}$ denotes the 2×2 minor formed by removing the 3rd and 4th rows and columns.

Definition 2. A totally positive matrix is a matrix whose minors are all positive.

Remark 1.2. All matrices we discuss in this paper will be totally positive.

Lemma 1.3. Any minor of an $n \times n$ square matrix is equivalent to a maximal ($n \times n$) minor of a $2n \times n$ matrix formed by concatenating (vertically) the original matrix with an anti-diagonal matrix whose entries have an absolute value of 1 and alternating sign.

Example 1.1. Let us find all minors of the matrix

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} \end{bmatrix}$$

First, let us consider the 1×1 minors. The minors $\Delta_{1,1}$, $\Delta_{1,2}$, $\Delta_{2,1}$, $\Delta_{2,2}$ are the minors created by removing all but one

column and row. Since the determinant of a single number is the number itself,

$$\Delta_{1,1} = x_{11}, \Delta_{1,2} = x_{12}, \Delta_{2,1} = x_{21}, \Delta_{2,2} = x_{22}$$

Then, we have the 2×2 minor, which is simply the minor created by removing zero columns. Therefore,

$$\Delta_{12,12} = \det A = x_{11}x_{21} - x_{21}x_{12}$$

Finally, let us consider the empty minor, where all column or rows are removed.

$$\Delta_{\emptyset} = 1$$

We now show Lemma 1.3 for $n = 2$ by considering the $2n \times 1$ matrix B such that

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} \\ 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The 2×2 minors of this matrix would be $\Delta_{12,12}, \Delta_{13,12}, \Delta_{14,12}, \Delta_{23,12}, \Delta_{24,12}, \Delta_{34,12}$. Computing the minors results in

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{12,12} &= x_{11}x_{21} - x_{21}x_{12}, \Delta_{13,12} = x_{11}, \Delta_{14,12} = x_{12} \\ \Delta_{23,12} &= x_{21}, \Delta_{24,12} = x_{22}, \Delta_{34,12} = 1 \end{aligned}$$

Note that since each of the maximal minors computed from the matrix B above is either an entry of matrix A (which is given by $A_{ij} = (a_{ij})$), the empty minor, or the determinant of the matrix A . So, it is clear that every maximal minor of B is equivalent to a minor of A , and vice versa.

Remark 1.4. We note that since there exists this bijection between minors of an $n \times n$ matrix and maximal minors of a $2n \times n$ matrix, we may refer to any $k \times k$ minor by one index set of the larger matrix. This index set I which indicates the kept rows is called the Plücker coordinates of a minor. The complement of I , denoted I^c , will simply be the set of missing indices from I .

Definition 3. Let us denote a sum of specific minors of a totally positive matrix as S_k . Here, S_k is given by the formula:

$$S_k = \binom{n}{k}^{-1} \sum_{\substack{|I|=k \\ I \subseteq [n]}} \det(A(I)) \det(A(I^c))$$

Remark 1.5. Another form of S_k is given by the equation,

$$S_k = \sum_{\substack{|I|=k \\ I \subseteq [n]}} \det(A(I)) \det(A(I^c))$$

In this paper we will focus on this second form of S_k . From here on out, S_k will denote this second form.

Definition 4. The Grassmannian, $Gr(k, V)$, is a space that parameterizes all k -dimensional linear subspaces of the n -dimensional vector space V .

Example 1.2.

- The Grassmannian $Gr(1, R^3)$ is the space of lines that pass through the origin in R^3 .
- Each point in $Gr(2, R^m)$ is a plane in R^m .

Remark 1.6. The set of Plücker coordinates corresponding to minors of a given matrix can be embedded in the Grassmannian space. The structure of this space induces relations between these Plücker coordinates which are called Plücker relations.

Definition 5. A Short Plücker relation is a Plücker relation between two minors whose index sets differ by exactly two values. The formula for these relations for some $2n \times n$ is given by:

$$|i_1 i_2 \dots a \dots b \dots i_n| |i_1 i_2 \dots \alpha \dots \beta \dots i_n| = |i_1 i_2 \dots a \dots \alpha \dots i_n| |i_1 i_2 \dots b \dots \beta \dots i_n| + |i_1 i_2 \dots \alpha \dots b \dots i_n| |i_1 i_2 \dots a \dots \beta \dots i_n|$$

Theorem 1.7. [3] The relation of S_k to S_{k-1} when $k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ is,

$$S_k \geq S_{k-1}$$

RESULTS

In this section we prove the inequality, from here on denoted (*),

$$S_k^2 \geq S_{k+1} \cdot S_{k-1} \iff S_k^2 - S_{k+1} \cdot S_{k-1} \geq 0$$

for all k of $n = 2, 3$ and 4 . We also proved the (*) for the arbitrary n and $k = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor, 1$.

Lemma 2.1. The following equivalence holds:

$$S_k = S_{n-k}$$

Proof. We note that

$$S_k = \sum_{\substack{|I|=k \\ I \subseteq [n]}} \det(A(I)) \det(A(I^c))$$

and

$$S_{n-k} = \sum_{\substack{|I|=n-k \\ I \subseteq [n]}} \det(A(I)) \det(A(I^c))$$

However, since the total amount of indices is n , any minor of the form $\det(A(I^c))$ in S_k will be exactly equal to a minor of the form $\det(A(I))$ in S_{n-k} and vice versa. Since this holds \forall minors in S_k ,

$$S_k = S_{n-k}$$

Lemma 2.2. If (*) holds for some k , (*) holds for $n - k$.

Proof. Assume (*) holds for some k . Then,

$$S_k^2 \geq S_{k+1} \cdot S_{k-1}$$

Noting $S_k = S_{n-k}$, $S_{k+1} = S_{n-k-1}$, and $S_{k-1} = S_{n-k+1}$, we see,

$$S_{n-k}^2 \geq S_{n-k-1} \cdot S_{n-k+1}$$

which is the desired inequality.

Lemma 2.3. (*) holds for all k when $n = 2$.

Proof. We note that for $n = 2$, the only possible value for k is 1 .

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} S_{k-1} &= S_0 = |12||34| \\ S_k = S_1 &= |13||24| + |24||13| = 2 \cdot |13||24| = 2 \cdot (|12||34| + |14||23|) \\ S_{k+1} &= S_2 = |12||34| \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} S_1^2 &= 4 \cdot (|12||34|)^2 + 2|12||34||14||23| + (|14||23|)^2 \\ S_0 S_2 &= (|12||34|)^2 \end{aligned}$$

So, (*) becomes:

$$S_1^2 - S_0 S_2 = 3 \cdot (|12||34|)^2 + 8 \cdot |12||34||14||23| + 4 \cdot (|14||23|)^2 \geq 0$$

as desired since all minors of this totally positive matrix are positive.

Lemma 2.4. (*) holds for all n , $k = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$

Proof. To prove this statement we examine two possible cases, when n is odd and when n is even:

• Odd n

Let $n = 2m + 1$. From Lemma 2.1 we know,

$$S_0 = S_{2m+1}, S_1 = S_{2m}, \dots, S_m = S_{m+1}.$$

Let $k = m$. Then,

$$S_m^2 - S_{m-1} S_{m+1} = S_m^2 - S_m S_{m-1} = S_m (S_m - S_{m-1}).$$

Since we know $S_k \geq S_{k-1}$ for $k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$, $S_m - S_{m-1} \geq 0$ and so, (*) holds

• Even n

Let $n = 2m$. From Lemma 2.1 we know,

$$S_0 = S_{2m}, S_1 = S_{2m-1}, \dots, S_{m-1} = S_{m+1}.$$

Let $k = m$. Then,

$$S_m^2 - S_{m-1} S_{m+1} = S_m^2 - S_{m-1}^2.$$

Since we know $S_k \geq S_{k-1}$ for $k \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$, $S_m^2 \geq S_{m-1}^2$ and so, (*) holds.

Thus, (*) holds for all n , $k = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$

Lemma 2.5. (*) holds for all k when $n = 4$

Proof. We shall begin by showing (*) holds for $n = 4$, $k = 1$.

Let us consider the terms of $S_{k-1}S_{k+1}$ and S_{k2} where $k = 1$ for some arbitrary 4×4 matrix.

$$S_0 = \sum_{\substack{|I|=0 \\ I \subseteq [4]}} \det(A(I)) \det(A(I^c)) = |1234|$$

$$S_1 = \sum_{\substack{|I|=1 \\ I \subseteq [4]}} \det(A(I)) \det(A(I^c)) = |1|234| + |2|134| + |3|124| + |4|123|$$

$$S_2 = \sum_{\substack{|I|=2 \\ I \subseteq [4]}} \det(A(I)) \det(A(I^c)) = |12|34| + |13|24| + |14|23| + |23|14| + |24|13| + |34|12|$$

Now, using Lemma 1.3, we construct the following 8×4 matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & x_{13} & x_{14} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & x_{23} & x_{24} \\ x_{31} & x_{32} & x_{33} & x_{34} \\ x_{41} & x_{42} & x_{43} & x_{44} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Note that the first block of four rows is simply the initial 4×4 matrix. We know by Lemma 1.3 that all 4×4 minors of this new matrix have the same determinant as all minors of the original matrix. Therefore, we can express the minors of S_{k-1} , S_{k+1} , and S_{k2} in terms of the new maximal minors from this 8×4 matrix. In doing so, we have

$$S_0 = |1234||5678|$$

$$S_1 = |1567||2348| + |2578||1347| + |3568||1247| + |4678||1235|$$

$$S_2 = |1256||3478| + |1357||2468| + |1467||2358| + |2358||1467| + |2468||1357| + |3478||1256|$$

Next consider S_0S_2 and S_1^2 .

$$S_0S_2 = |1234||5678|(|1256||3478| + |1357||2468|$$

$$+ |1467||2358| + |2358||1467| + |2468||1357| + |3478||1256|)$$

$$= |1234||5678||1256||3478| + |1234||5678||1357||2468| + |1234||5678||1467||2358|$$

$$+ |1234||5678||2358||1467| + |1234||5678||2468||1357| + |1234||5678||3478||1256|$$

$$S_1^2 = (|1567||2348| + |2568||1347| + |3568||1247| + |4678||1235|)^2$$

$$= |1567||2348||1567||2348| + |1567||2348||2568||1347| + |1567||2348||3568||1247|$$

$$+ |1567||2348||4678||1235| + |2568||1347||1567||2348| + |2568||1347||2578||1347|$$

$$+ |2568||1347||3568||1247| + |2568||1347||4678||1235| + |3568||1247||1567||2348|$$

$$+ |3568||1247||2568||1347| + |3568||1247||3568||1247| + |3568||1247||4678||1235|$$

$$+ |4678||1235||1567||2348| + |4678||1235||2568||1347| + |4678||1235||3568||1247|$$

$$+ |4678||1235||4678||1235|$$

Consider some term in S_0S_2 . Every term in S_0S_2 is given by a product of four minors: $|1234||5678||abcd||\alpha\beta\gamma\delta|$, where $a, b, c, d, \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ are all unique indices from one to eight. Based on this term, select the term in S_1^2

$$|acdy||ba\beta\delta||bcdy||\alpha\alpha\beta\gamma|$$

Using short Plücker relations twice on this term results in

$$|1234||5678||abcd||\alpha\beta\gamma\delta| + \dots$$

where the terms denoted by “...” are all positive because short

Plücker relations always yield positive results. Therefore, applying short Plücker relations to the six terms of the form described above in S_{12} creates all terms in S_{0S_2} and some other positive terms. Therefore, the expression $S_{12} - S_{0S_2}$ is subtraction free, as all terms in S_{0S_2} are canceled out. Since the remaining terms are all positive, $S_{12} - S_{0S_2} \geq 0$. Thus, (*) holds for $n = 4, k = 1$. For $n = 4, k = 2$: (*) holds by Lemma 2.4. For $n = 4, k = 3$: (*) holds by Lemma 2.2, as we proved that when $n = 4$, the inequality holds for $k = 1$. Thus, the inequality is proved for $n = 4$ and all k .

Lemma 2.6. (*) holds for $k = 1$ for all n Proof. Let us first examine $(S_1)_2$. We note that in $(S_1)_2$ there are two types of elements. First, there are n terms which are products of the same exact 1×1 minor (and its complement). (for $n = 4$ one such element would be $|1567||2348||1567||2348|$). Then, there are $n^2 - n$ terms which are the products of two different 1×1 minors (and their respective complements). However, only half of these products (or $\binom{n}{2}$) are unique. This is due to the fact that when S_{12} is expanded—say it includes two minors a and b —both ab and ba appear. Now, take an arbitrary element of these $\binom{n}{2}$ products. Since this is a product of two different 1×1 minors (and their complements), the Plücker coordinates of the minors (and respectively their complements) will differ exactly by two indices. In other words, the product of these minors would have the following form:

$$[\alpha, c_2, \dots, \psi, \dots, c_n] * [\beta, c_2, \dots, \omega, \dots, c_n]$$

where

$$\alpha, \beta \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \text{ and } c_2, \dots, c_n, \psi, \omega \in \{n + 1, \dots, 2n\}.$$

A similar pattern holds for the product of the complement of these two minors. So, a short 6 Plücker relation can be applied to both the product of these two minors and the product of the complements. For the product of the two above minors this yields:

$$[\alpha, \beta, c_2, \dots, c_n] * [c_2, \dots, \psi, \dots, \omega, \dots, c_n] + [\alpha, c_2, \dots, \omega, \dots, c_n] * [\beta, c_2, \dots, \psi, \dots, c_n]$$

We may number these terms I, II, III, and IV, respectively. Then, when a short Plücker relation is applied to the product of these two 1×1 minors complements, this yields:

$$I^c * II^c + III^c * IV^c$$

Then, when these two expressions are multiplied back together the final expression has the form:

$$I * II * I^c * II^c + I * II * III^c * IV^c + III * IV * I^c * II^c + III * IV * III^c * IV^c$$

Now, let us examine the very first term, $I * II * I^c * II^c$. We note that I is the Plücker coordinate of a 2×2 minor, so, I^c is a term that appears in S_2 . Furthermore, II is the empty minor as all n indices inside it are in the set $\{n + 1, \dots, 2n\}$. So, II^c is the

single element of S_0 . Finally, we may note the following: for each unique product of two different 1×1 minors, the two values α and β are unique, so they correspond to a unique element in S_2 , and thus a unique element in $S_2 * S_0$. Additionally, we know that there are

$$\binom{n}{k-1} * \binom{n}{k+1} = \binom{n}{2} * \binom{n}{0} = 1 * \binom{n}{2} = \binom{n}{2}$$

terms in the product $S_2 * S_0$. So, if we recall that there are

$$\binom{n}{k-1} * \binom{n}{k+1} = \binom{n}{2} * \binom{n}{0} = 1 * \binom{n}{2} = \binom{n}{2}$$

unique products of 1×1 minors (that all yield different 222 products of a 2×2 minor and the empty minor), we can see that every term in $S_2 * S_0$ can be created using a short Plücker relation and some term in S_{12} . So, when examining the inequality $S_{12} - S_0 S_2 \geq 0$, all the terms in $S_0 S_2$ can be cancelled through short Plücker relations applied to $n^2 - n$ unique terms in S_{12} leaving only some residual terms of S_{12} . However, all of these residual terms are still minors of a totally positive matrix, so they are all greater than 0. Thus, $S_{12}^2 - S_0 S_2 \geq 0$ for all n .

Next, we focus our attention on the cluster that the Plücker coordinates are a part of.

Lemma 2.7. The cluster associated with the Plücker coordinates of an arbitrary $n \times n$ matrix can be constructed through a general algorithm.

Proof. We know the following for minors in the cluster:

$$P_0 = |12 \dots n|, P_1 = |(n+1)(n+2) \dots (2n)|;$$

For $1 \leq i \leq n-1$, we must have $1 \leq j \leq 2n+1-2i$. We get the generalized expression for P_{ij} :

$$P_{ij} = \begin{cases} |(n-i+1-j+1) \dots (n-i+1-j+i)(n+1) \dots (2n-i)|, & \text{if } 1 \leq j \leq n-i+1 \\ |1 \dots i(n+1) \dots (n+2n-2i-j+1)(3n-i-j+2) \dots (2n)|, & \text{if } n-i+1 < j \leq 2n+1-2i \end{cases}$$

Figure 1. Example paths change of $n = 6$.

where the dots represent consecutive increasing numbers. These P_{ij} 's together with P_0 and P_1 form the cluster of minors. Figure 1 illustrates an example of the case of $n = 6$.

It is obvious to see P_0 and P_1 , and the leftmost P_{ij} 's, so it suffices to show the change from P_{ij} to $P_{i(j+1)}$.

Consider the move from P_{ij} to $P_{i(j+1)}$. The edge it crosses flips direction, thus determines the one and only one change of the row index. We first consider the case where the P_{ij} 's are on the left side of the graph, i.e., $1 \leq j \leq n-i$. The sink of the original path of P_{ij} is completely determined by the number of edges to the left of P_{ij} , $j-1$, thus the sink is $n-(j-1)$. Similarly, the sink of the new path is $n-(j-1)+i$. So a move from P_{ij} to $P_{i(j+1)}$ will change $n-(j-1)$ in the minor index to $n-(j-1)+i$.

Next we consider the case where the $P_{i(j+1)}$'s are on the right side, i.e., $n-i+1 \leq j < 2n+1-2i$. Similar to the previous argument, the sink of the original path is determined by the number of edges to the right of $P_{i(j+1)}$, that is $n+2n+1-2i-j$. And similarly, the move to the right will cause an increase of i in the sink index. So a move from P_{ij} to $P_{i(j+1)}$ will change $3n-2i-j+1$ in the minor index to $3n-i-j+1$.

It is now obvious to verify the general expression by induction.

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College of Science Student & Alumni Spotlights

Eva Deegan

Environmental Sciences

Author: Maggie Watson

Q: So, Eva, what inspired your passion for environmental science?

Eva: That's funny; I actually always joke about how in high school, I took a BuzzFeed quiz that said to go into "environmental science," and I never looked back.

~

Various research experiences and one college degree later, there you have it: living proof that BuzzFeed quizzes are, in fact, the final frontier in accurate aptitude tests.

Eva Deegan is a senior in the final stretch of her environmental science major and data science minor at Notre Dame. She found her entryway into research through the Jones Lab, focusing on aquatic ecology in order to understand how different organisms and vegetation contribute to processes like carbon transport for entire ecosystems.

With growing interest and experience, her next step was involvement in the University of Notre Dame Environmental Research Center (UNDERC). She recounts fond memories of an excursion with a team from Notre Dame to an UNDERC property in northern Wisconsin, where she worked as part of the limnology team. Committed to specific analysis of lake impact on lateral carbon transport, some day-to-day activities of this research included going to different lake areas, collecting organism and vegetation samples, heading back in the afternoon to process all the samples, and analyzing these findings. "The nearest grocery store was like 40 minutes away; it was so isolated, so immersed in the outdoors, and such an amazing experience," Deegan says, beaming. Her propensity for the environmental sciences derives from her love for the outdoors, which is heavily integrated into the type of research offered through UNDERC.

She pursued her own personal study under the guidance of mentor Ceara Talbot, whom Deegan greatly admires. Talbot's prerogative was to establish that lateral carbon transport in lake ecosystems was a missing piece of the carbon data-modeling puzzle. The neglect of this data around lakes rendered current models inaccurate by her research claims. Deegan's personal report, "Drought-driven changes in terrestrial water use efficiency impact lateral carbon transport," was a study created to validate Talbot's findings. It actually resulted in the conclusion that the original data modeling tool was more accurate, but despite the lack of validation or expected outcome, Deegan spoke of this experience as an important step in the learning process and an unavoidable part of academic research.

In the future, she is interested in working in either ecological modeling or environmental data management, two aspects of the research she has done while here at Notre Dame. Branching out from aquatic to terrestrial environments interests her, as do the dynamics surrounding big data, climate science, and building trust with the public by using data to help convey information in a digestible, readable way. Whether the product of a BuzzFeed quiz, immersive experiences in research, or a combination, environmental science for Deegan is both a passion and a "natural fit." Her work has been a manifestation of doing what she loves, and shedding a light on Deegan also provides a deserving spotlight to all the vital work regarding assessment and alleviation of environmental impacts on our planet.

James Galante

Science Computing

Author: Ella Hall

Sometimes it can take time to find out what kind of research you're interested in as you navigate the twists and turns of college life while exploring undergraduate research. Take James Galante, a senior here at Notre Dame majoring in science computing.

Galante first thought he wanted to be a doctor, but after doing a neurosurgery clerkship, he realized it wasn't for him. After coming to Notre Dame, he bounced from bioengineering research, to an organic chemistry lab, to a computational neuroscience lab. These experiences exposed him to coding, AI, virus sampling, and sequencing, but he wanted to gain more wet lab experience. Galante found his current home in Dr. Christopher Patzke's lab

investigating neuropathological conditions with a neurobiology focus. In the Patzke Lab, Galante works on a disease called Miller-Dieker syndrome, which is a rare genetic disorder that affects brain development and can cause neurological problems. Galante's work involves performing RNA sequencing experiments to characterize cells or find the difference in gene programs between diseased and regular cells, and he does this from a computational perspective. Galante described RNA sequencing as a "very robust way to describe a system" and believes that it is the future of biology. This research has the potential to identify therapeutic targets and inform the development of treatments for Miller-Dieker syndrome and other neurodevelopmental disorders.

Galante has advice for Notre Dame students hoping to get into undergraduate research: Remember that PIs are people. Rather than simply listing your accomplishments and plans, Galante recommends coming from a more friendly stance. When he got into his current lab, he emailed and asked if he could shadow someone for a day to see what it was like. He was told to keep coming in day after day, and it was an easy transition into the lab because he was a person, not just paragraphs of accomplishments. "If you get your foot in the door, if you introduce yourself as an individual and not a prospective lab member, it's a lot easier."

While it took him some time to find a lab that fit him, Galante has a passion for research evident in the way that his eyes light up while explaining every minutiae of his work. His favorite part of research? "I love being on the frontier of science," Galante says, and he believes that it's important to understand the world around you so that you can have an opinion on what's in the news, things like COVID-19 and ChatGPT. Galante disclosed his plans to work as a computational biologist for a research laboratory at Stanford University next year with intention to later attend graduate school in the field. Wherever he goes, he'll carry his excitement for discovering more about the world. "Having the right insight isn't enough," Galante says. "You have to ask the right questions."

Grace Bradley

Neuroscience and Behavior

Author: Sofia Zitella

Title of research publication or topic: "COVID-19 Isolation and Its Impact on Marital Relationships"

How did you become involved in undergraduate research?

In high school I loved doing research and science fairs, and after graduating I spent some time at Central State University researching bees and their DNA. I have always loved working in labs and asking questions. After the fall of my sophomore year, we had a long winter break and I wanted to get involved in research. I love neuroscience and the neuroscience faculty at Notre Dame, so I reached out to Dr. Cindy Bergeman, who at the time was collecting data on COVID-19.

What is your research topic and details of the lab in which you research?

I work with the Adult Development and Aging Lab with Dr. Bergeman. When I joined the lab, we were collecting data showing that from March 2019 to March 2020, domestic violence rates increased drastically. Some couples said that the pandemic was horrible for their relationship, and some said it was the best thing that happened for their marriage. I wanted to know why, what happy couples were doing differently, and why domestic violence rates were increasing. Participants completed daily diaries that asked about their relationships and emotions, and we tracked their cortisol, medical history, and other biomarkers. Our goal was to see how a period of isolation—during which adults dealt with threats to their health, job, and lifestyle—impacted their outlook on their marriage.

Do you plan to publish your research, and if so, where?

I am working on a joint thesis between the Glynn Honors Program and the Neuroscience Honors Program. I hope to publish my research; I do not know where yet, but a lot of research from my lab has been published by *The Gerontologist*.

Do you have any advice for Notre Dame students hoping to be involved with research at Notre Dame and for those who want to publish their research?

The most difficult part about getting started is having to put yourself out there. I emailed a bunch of people in my department, and you have to be okay with accepting "no's." It is difficult approaching someone with so much more experience than you, but it is vital to own that you have questions, and that you want to grow and learn. Publishing is difficult because you will receive many different opinions, but remember to keep the end in sight. Not everyone gets published, but you are not just doing research to get your name in a journal. Your primary objective is to learn!

College of Science Student/Alumni Spotlights

Daniel O'Shea

Biology and Economics (pre-med)

Author: Avery Njau

Title of research publication or topic: “Wild-type SARS-CoV-2 neutralizing immunity decreases across variants and over time but correlates well with diagnostic testing”

How did you become involved in undergraduate research?

I reached out to the University of Michigan through a family friend and got in touch with a professor through the Mary H. Weiser Food Allergy Center. I was supposed to be working on a different project, but after a mishap occurred with the original lab, I got the opportunity to work in the SARS-CoV-2 lab instead. I worked there for twelve weeks after receiving a research grant through the Glynn Family Honors Program.

What is your research topic and the details of the lab in which you research?

I worked in a very hands-on lab at the University of Michigan this past summer, where I started performing pseudoviral neutralization assays as soon as I got there. The lab focused on the degree of immunity against various SARS-CoV-2 variants provided by vaccination with wild-type virus versus infection from the virus. The research found that participants who had both a previous infection and vaccination had the highest level of neutralizing antibodies against all variants. It also supported the concept of future SARS-CoV-2 booster vaccines that are specific to the omicron variant.

What journal do you plan to submit your research to, or where have you previously published your research?

My research was published by *Frontiers in Immunology*.

Do you have any advice for Notre Dame students hoping to be involved with research at Notre Dame and for those who want to publish their research?

Get on it early. I wish that I could have gotten involved a little earlier on, but unfortunately COVID made research inaccessible. Finding what you're interested in can really lead you down a path of doing publishable research. In terms of applying to

grants, trying your best and really staying on top of deadlines is the best way to tackle them. Reaching out to professors to help fine-tune your grants is also very helpful, because lots of times research funding goes to those who can write the best grant proposals!

Aidan Crowley

Alumna—Neuroscience & Behavior

Author: Josh Moeller

Aidan Crowley graduated from Notre Dame in 2021, where she majored in neuroscience with minors in compassionate care in medicine and poverty studies. She was also the former *Scientia* co-editor-in-chief for Vol. 12 Spring 2021.

During her time at Notre Dame, Crowley spent the summer following her freshman year at a Summer Service Learning Program in Kalamazoo, Michigan, shadowing at Bronson Methodist Hospital while living at the Hospital Hospitality House (similar to a Ronald McDonald house) nearby. She credits this experience of both living and working around patients with sparking her passion for clinical medicine as well as understanding the importance of compassionate care in medicine.

Crowley went on to spend her second summer performing undergraduate research at Mayo Clinic Summer Undergraduate Program in Biomedical Ethics Research where she studied stem cell ethics—looking at the unethical language found in advertisements for private stem cell firms that lacked strong regulatory oversight. She would continue this research while studying abroad in Copenhagen, Denmark, at a partner laboratory located there.

Despite the COVID pandemic, Crowley returned to campus for her final summer at Notre Dame. Here, she partnered with the Ruth M. Hillebrand Center for Compassionate Care in Medicine to perform the research that would make up her Glynn thesis—an interview study of emergency department ICU physicians and how they embodied compassion during the COVID-19 public health crisis.

After graduating from Notre Dame, Crowley immediately matriculated to medical school at the University of Pennsylvania's

Perelman School of Medicine, where she is currently completing clinical rotations. During her first year of medical school, Crowley decided to pursue a dual MD-Ph.D. In her initial experiences at the University of Pennsylvania, she quickly realized that medical school did not develop the full range of skills necessary to address the questions she wanted to examine. As part of her pursuit of a Ph.D. in healthcare management and economics, Crowley works with the Leonard Davis Institute of Health Economics. In this role, she works with the payment insight team studying how physician groups are paid and how reimbursement design affects incentives for clinical decision-making. As part of this project, they also develop various alternative payment models and examine how hospitals react to them.

Outside of this work, Crowley was also heavily involved in the Philadelphia community, volunteering both at Children's Hospital of Philadelphia Homeless Health Initiative and University City Hospitality Coalition (a student-run free clinic).

Who was your biggest mentor during your time at Notre Dame and how did they influence you?

Dr. Dominic Vachon really influenced me. First of all, we did research together, and just through working together on projects like my Glynn thesis, he helped me a lot. But, honestly, part of having a good mentor is having meetings that aren't directly related to the work you are doing. Dr. Vachon spent a lot of time meeting with me just to ask how I am doing, how he can help, whether my career goals have changed, or even to discuss news articles that we think are interesting. I think what made him a great mentor was not only the practical support like writing reference letters, but also the level of support he gave to my broader development as a researcher. We still keep in touch today—sending articles we find interesting back and forth and meeting once a semester just to check in. I can't overstate how important it is to keep in touch with mentors you have had in the past; you never know when you'll need to rely on your network, so even keeping in touch in small ways goes a really long way.

As you know, a lot of students enter their undergrad thinking they want to go to medical school, but it is often difficult to be sure about pursuing such a long and difficult process. Do you have any discernment advice for unsure pre-med undergraduate students?

The way that the medical application process has been going, there's been increased focus on research, leadership, and volunteering. All of these are really great, but at the end of the day medical school is turning you into a doctor—a clinician. I would strongly advocate for as much experience with clinical medicine as you can possibly get. My clinical experiences were what I talked about in interviews and wrote about in

my personal statement; remember the people reviewing your application are clinical doctors. There's also so much value for discernment in clinical experience. You are signing up for a very long career, and the better understanding you have of what you are actually doing as a physician is essential. My advice is to do the widest breadth of clinical experiences possible, don't focus on just one field, because different specialties have wildly different day-to-day lives.

TALK SCIENCE

FEBRUARY 16, 2023

Dr. Evan Kirby
Department of Physics and Astronomy
Associate Professor
“Galactic Archaeology”

Audrey Miles
Chemistry '23
“Exploring Cation-Mediated
Equilibria in Uranyl Polyoxometalate
Systems”

MARCH 1, 2023

Dr. Rebecca Wingert
Department of Biological Sciences
Director of Graduate Studies
“Genetic Mechanisms of Multiciliated
Cell Development”

Allison Healy
Biological Sciences '24
“The Role of amt in Nephrogenesis”

MARCH 22, 2023

Dr. Keith Davis
Department of Physics and Astronomy
Associate Professor
“A Vision for Life in the Solar System.”
at the Digital Visualization Theater

Grace Bradley
Neuroscience & Behavior '23
“COVID-19 Isolation and Marital
Relationships”

APRIL 19, 2023

Dr. Holly Goodson
Department of Chemistry & Biochemistry
Professor; Director, IBS Graduate Program
“What aspects of (cell) biology are
predictable?”

Brooke Friedman
Neuroscience & Behavior '24
“Pattern Similarity Analysis of
Episodic Memory Using EEG”

Talk Science is a seminar series organized by *Scientia* that invites undergraduate students and faculty to present their research in an informal setting. These seminars are open to all students and faculty at the University of Notre Dame. Each semester there are three to four Talk Science events with topics that cover the many different science disciplines within the College of Science.

PUBLISH

Interested in publishing your research in the next issue of *Scientia* or presenting at the next Talk Science seminar?
Email the editors at scientia@nd.edu.

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